

Identifying key predictors of mid-childhood obesity in a population-based cohort study: An evidence synthesis and predictive modeling study

Yuchan Mou^{1, 2}, Susana Santos^{2, 3, 4}, Macarena Lara¹, Ivonne P.M. Derks^{5, 6, 7}, Vincent W.V. Jaddoe^{1, 2, 3}, Romy Gaillard^{1, 2, 3}, Janine F. Felix^{2, 3}, Eric Steegers⁸, Trudy Voortman^{1, 9}, Marinus H. van IJzendoorn^{10, 11}, Pauline W. Jansen^{5, 6}

Affiliations

1. Department of Epidemiology, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, The Netherlands
2. The Generation R Study Group, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, The Netherlands
3. Department of Pediatrics, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, The Netherlands
4. EPIUnit ITR, Instituto de Saúde Pública da Universidade do Porto, Universidade do Porto, Rua das Taipas, n° 135, 4050-600 Porto, Portugal
5. Department of Psychology, Education and Child Studies, Erasmus University Rotterdam, The Netherlands
6. Department of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry / Psychology, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, The Netherlands
7. Research Department of Behavioural Science and Health, University College London, United Kingdom
8. Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, Netherlands
9. Meta-Research Innovation Center at Stanford (METRICS), Stanford University, Stanford, CA, USA

Predictors of child BMI

10. Department of Psychiatry, Monash University, Melbourne, Australia

11. Research Department of Clinical, Education and Health Psychology, UCL, University of London, UK

Funding

The general design of the Generation R Study is made possible by financial support from Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, Erasmus University Rotterdam, the Netherlands Organization for Health Research and Development (ZonMw), Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO), Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport and Ministry of Youth and Families. Yuchan Mou is supported by China Scholarship Council PhD Fellowship (201806240125) for her PhD study in Erasmus Medical Center, Rotterdam, the Netherlands. Susana Santos is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship Grant Agreement No. 101109136 (URBANE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Pauline Jansen is supported by a grant from ZonMw (Mental Health Care Research Program—Fellowship 636320005). This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (733206, LIFECYCLE; 848158, EarlyCause; 874739, LongITools)

The funders had no role in the study design, data collection, management, analysis and interpretation of data, and preparation or writing the manuscript.

Corresponding author: Pauline W. Jansen, Dr. Molewaterplein 40, PO Box 2040, 3000 CA, Rotterdam, the Netherlands, p.w.jansen@erasmusmc.nl

Conflict of interest statement: The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

1 **Summary**

2 A wide spectrum of predictors of childhood overweight and obesity has been identified over past decades,
3 yet a quantitative overview of multidisciplinary predictors is missing, and the relative importance and their
4 collective contribution to childhood obesity remains unclear. We synthesized evidence from 93 published
5 studies from the Generation R Study, a population-based prospective cohort from early-pregnancy onwards
6 in the Netherlands, to provide a quantitative overview of 210 predictors across preconception and childhood
7 associated with body mass index (BMI) in mid-childhood and selected 59 candidate predictors. Then, we
8 further identified 32 key predictors for either zBMI or weight status using model search algorithms and
9 built prediction models with data from the same cohort. Associations of note were identified between
10 predictors in preconception and prenatal parental health, early-life weight, and child behavior domains. A
11 interquartile range increase in predictor was positively associated with mid-childhood BMI for parental
12 prepregnancy BMI (maternal $\beta=0.17$, 95% CI: 0.14, 0.20; paternal $\beta=0.17$, 95% CI: 0.14, 0.21), early-life
13 weight (e.g., zBMI at age 2y $\beta=0.28$, 95% CI: 0.23, 0.33), and food responsiveness ($\beta=0.25$, 95% CI: 0.21,
14 0.28), and negatively with satiety responsiveness ($\beta=-0.18$, 95% CI: -0.21, -0.15). Together, key predictors
15 accounted for 49.2% of the variance of BMI and 33.7% of the variance of the odds of overweight and
16 obesity at the age of 10 years. Multimodal interventions targeting parental BMI before pregnancy, early
17 adiposity rebound, and management of appetite in early childhood may be most effective in maintaining a
18 healthy weight during childhood.

19 **Key words:** systematic review, predictors, BMI, childhood obesity, longitudinal population-based study,
20 explained variance

21 **Abbreviations:** BMI, body mass index; DSA, deletion-substitution-addition; PUFA, polysaturated fatty
22 acids; AA, arachidonic acid; DTA, docosatetraenoic acid; 25(OH)D, 25-hydroxyvitamin D; FFQ, food-
23 frequency questionnaire; SNP, single nucleotide polymorphism; PRS, polygenic risk score; SDS
24 standardized deviation score; BSI, Brief Symptom Inventory; GSI, Global Severity Index; CFQ, Child

Predictors of child BMI

- 25 Feeding Questionnaire; CEBQ, Children's Eating Behavior Questionnaire; LC-MS, liquid chromatography
- 26 tandem mass spectrometry; R^2 , coefficient of determination; h^2 , narrow-sense heritability.

27 **Introduction**

28 Childhood obesity is a major, global public health problem. Although the rising trends have plateaued in
29 many developed countries, the prevalence of childhood obesity remains alarmingly high¹. This concern is
30 amplified by evidence that child overweight and obesity often persists into adulthood^{2,3}. Greater body mass
31 index (BMI) and adiposity are associated with an increased risk of psychological problems^{4,5}, and with
32 disturbances in cardiometabolic health indicators throughout the life course⁶, including cardiovascular
33 diseases and type 2 diabetes, which can lead to premature death^{7,8}.

34 Identifying key predictors is an important step towards early detection of childhood obesity and monitoring
35 of those at risk of obesity. In the past two decades, epidemiological studies have investigated a wide
36 spectrum of predictors of overweight and obesity at different ages in childhood, spanning from demographic,
37 socioeconomic, environmental, and genetic to behavioral factors. A comprehensive overview of these
38 candidate predictors and their effect sizes from preconception onwards will provide evidence for predicting
39 child BMI from a life course perspective. Indeed, many systematic reviews and meta-analyses collected
40 evidence for candidate predictors of child BMI, yet these overviews did not uncover predictors exhaustively.
41 On the one hand, some systematic reviews evaluated evidence for various predictors in a narrative form⁹,
42 ¹⁰, and thereby lacked quantitative assessment of effect. On the other hand, meta-analyses estimate overall
43 measures of effect, and typically included only a limited number of predictors, often focusing on a cluster
44 of predictors, such as dietary factors or physical activity¹¹. As such, a quantitative overview of predictors
45 from a multidisciplinary perspective is missing. Therefore, we propose to review predictors in a single
46 longitudinal cohort to go beyond a traditional review, including multidisciplinary predictors measured with
47 the advantage of homogeneity of study design and sampling, despite potential limitations in generalizability.

48 Another important gap in the identification of key predictors of childhood obesity is that predictors are
49 often examined independently in epidemiological studies, making it hard to draw conclusion on the
50 importance of predictors and their collective contribution to childhood obesity. Joint testing of multiple

51 predictors may reveal the ones that are most strongly, and independently of other factors, associated with
52 child BMI, as well as estimate the extent to which key predictors contribute to variation in child BMI.
53 Research into multi-exposures and their associations with childhood obesity has been explored within the
54 exposome field to identify relevant environmental features¹². Environmental features constitute one aspect
55 of the multifactorial influences contributing to childhood obesity. However, a more comprehensive
56 perspective including individual behavioral characteristics remains largely unexplored. Jointly testing all
57 potential predictors of a health outcome presents a significant conceptual and data feasibility challenge.
58 Through evidence synthesis within a single cohort, we can employ both hypothesis-driven and exploratory
59 approaches to identify key predictors and their cumulative explanation of the variance in a specific health
60 outcome measured in the same cohort across time. This approach maximizes within-study variation by
61 minimizing between-study variability that might often be difficult to explain in regular meta-analytic
62 syntheses of several independent samples. The single cohort approach may increase internal validity at the
63 expense of external validity, and the generalizability of the resulting predictive model should be tested in
64 (the combination of) other cohort studies.

65 In this study, we aimed to integrate domain-specific knowledge by using published studies from the
66 Generation R Study, a large prospective cohort with measurements encompassing genetic,
67 sociodemographic, behavioral factors from fetal life onwards, to facilitate selecting predictors from a
68 multidisciplinary view. We aimed 1) to provide a quantitative overview of predictors across pregnancy and
69 childhood associated with BMI in mid-childhood, 2) to identify which of these predictors are most relevant,
70 and to explore how much variance in child BMI these key predictors together explain. First, we performed
71 a systematic review of Generation R papers describing associations of any predictor with child BMI and
72 quantitatively synthesized the evidence to present the magnitudes of associations. Second, based on the
73 results from the quantitative synthesis, we selected candidate predictors using a pre-defined magnitude of
74 effect estimates, and we used an iterative model search algorithm to further select a subset of the most
75 relevant predictors using data from the Generation R Study. We assessed the joint associations between

76 these key predictors with child BMI and weight status in mid-childhood. We focused on BMI and weight
77 status in middle childhood because this stage represents a critical developmental period when obesity and
78 its related behaviors persist into adulthood^{3, 13, 14}. Moreover, obesity in mid-childhood is associated with a
79 range of short and long-term health outcomes, including cardiometabolic health, as well as psychosocial
80 outcomes later in life^{15, 16}. Identifying predictors of mid-childhood BMI is therefore crucial for uncovering
81 intervention opportunities that can have sustained, long-term health benefits.

82 **Methods**

83 **Study population**

84 The Generation R Study is an ongoing population-based prospective cohort from early fetal life onward in
85 Rotterdam, the Netherlands¹⁷, which is designed to identify early environmental and genetic determinants
86 of growth, development and health during the life course. Of the included pregnant women with a delivery
87 date between April 2002 to January 2006, 7393 mother-child pairs consented for follow-up in the mid-
88 childhood. BMI at age 10 years was measured in 5686 children. The study was approved by the Medical
89 Ethics Committee of Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam. Written informed consent was
90 obtained from parents of all participating children.

91 **Evidence synthesis**

92 **Study selection**

93 All published studies using data from the Generation R Study were eligible. We searched for literature in
94 the electronic databases: PubMed, Embase, Ovid MEDLINE and Web of science. The search strategy
95 consisted of combinations of the names of main researchers of the Generation R Study to ensure inclusion
96 of all the Generation R Study publications for screening, including those that examined BMI in additional
97 or secondary analyses instead of in main analyses (see detailed information of search strategies in
98 **Supplementary Methods 1**). Searches were restricted to studies published until October 31st, 2023.

99 We defined the eligibility criteria prior to the study. Studies were included if they: (1) Used primary data
100 from the Generation R Study; (2) Were conducted in the full Generation R Study sample, i.e. studies on
101 sub-cohorts with specific selection criteria applied were excluded (e.g., the Focus cohort of mother and
102 child pairs (n=1232), a sample of families of Dutch origin selected for in-depth assessments)¹⁷; (3) Assessed
103 child BMI or zBMI as an outcome between the ages of 2 and 10 years; (4) Reported adequate details to
104 perform the calculation of effect estimates. Duplicates were removed before screening. Three reviewers
105 (YM, ML, TV) screened independently. First, titles and abstracts were screened. Second, full-texts of
106 selected papers were reviewed based on inclusion criteria; each step was done by two reviewers.
107 Disagreements on study eligibility were resolved via discussion between reviewers, or with senior
108 researchers (MvIJ, PJ) when uncertainty persisted. In addition, we conducted a cross-checking with the
109 Generation R Study internal publication repository during the full-text screening stage and added papers
110 that were missed during the database search. The screening process is presented in a PRISMA 2020 flow
111 diagram¹⁸ (**Figure 1**).

112 **Data extraction**

113 The extracted information included the name of first author, year of publication, measurement of predictors,
114 ages at assessment of predictors and outcomes, standard deviations of predictors and outcomes necessary
115 for data conversion, sample size (total sample size, and sample sizes in reference group and comparison
116 groups when available), covariates, statistical analysis performed, effect measures, and if available, effect
117 estimates. Six reviewers (YM, ML, ID, TV, MvIJ, PJ) independently extracted data using a standardized
118 data extraction form. All extracted data were checked by the first author (YM) for accuracy. Additional
119 decisions were made when extracting data: (1) If multiple measurements of BMI were reported separately
120 in one study, only the effect estimates for BMI at the latest time-point (i.e. the oldest age) were extracted
121 to use data spanning the largest time window; (2) Moderation effect estimates (i.e. effect modification)
122 were not included as our focus was on main effects; (3) Effect estimates of continuous (or ordinal)
123 predictors were prioritized over categorical predictors; (4) When the standard deviation of BMI was not

124 presented in a study, interquartile, 90% or 95% range (depending on whichever presented) was extracted;
125 (5) Effect estimates were extracted from the mean differences, bivariate correlation matrix, basic models
126 and confounder-adjusted models, with the unadjusted effect sizes (mean differences, bivariate correlations
127 or basic/unadjusted models) being prioritized to enhance comparability of effect sizes across papers. When
128 no unadjusted effect estimates were presented, the models most minimally adjusted for confounders were
129 considered as proxies to unadjusted effect sizes. For studies with multiple comparison groups, the number
130 of participants in the reference group was divided evenly among the comparisons to address the unit-of-
131 analysis error¹⁹.

132 **Quantitative syntheses**

133 All reported effect estimates - β (standardized regression coefficient), B (unstandardized regression
134 coefficient), mean, median and r (correlation) - were converted to Fisher's z to facilitate confidence interval
135 computation in the quantitative synthesis. All conversions were done in R 3.6.1 using the 'esc' package²⁰
136 and customized R functions²¹⁻²³ and are summarized in **Table S1** and **Table S2**.

137 We used the random-effect model to pool the effect estimates of predictors representing a similar construct
138 that were assessed at different ages (e.g., effect estimates of food responsiveness at ages 4 and 10 years on
139 child BMI at age 10 years were pooled)²⁴, because we assume effect estimates of a predictor may vary
140 between studies exploring different developmental stages. We used Fishers' z to pool effect estimates of
141 predictors, and then converted them to Cohen's d (95% CI) to present the summary effect sizes.

142 Considering the large variety of predictors included and that effect estimates yielded in a large population-
143 based cohort study are generally small, we defined $|d| \geq 0.1$ as the threshold value of effect sizes for
144 selecting candidate predictors with substantial effect. We clustered candidate predictors into nine domains.
145 Forest plots were constructed for candidate predictors. Quantitative syntheses were run in R 3.6.1 using the
146 'meta' package, and forest plots were constructed using the 'ggplot2' package.

147 **Predictive modeling**

148 Based on the results of quantitative synthesis, prediction models of BMI and weight status were built using
149 data from the Generation R Study.

150 **Childhood obesity outcomes**

151 At the age of 10 years, children's weight was measured without shoes and heavy clothing, using a
152 mechanical personal scale (SECA, Almere, the Netherlands), and height was measured with a Harpenden
153 stadiometer (Holtain Limited, DYFED, U.K.) by trained staff during visits to the Generation R research
154 center at the Erasmus MC using standard procedures. BMI was calculated as weight/height^2 (kg/m^2) and
155 we further calculated age- and sex-specific standard BMI z-scores (zBMI) according to the Dutch reference
156 growth curves²⁵ constructed using the LMS method with data from a nation-wide growth study sampling
157 and measuring children up to 20 years of age in 1996 and 1997, and we categorized BMI into weight status
158 according to the International Obesity Task Force (IOTF) cutoffs²⁶. We chose to use zBMI as an outcome
159 because it allows us to highlight predictors that contribute to deviations from typical growth patterns within
160 the Dutch population, which is more relevant for identifying at-risk children and public health interventions.
161 Furthermore, it allows comparison between studies.

162 **Measurement of selected candidate predictors**

163 The detailed description on how information of the selected candidate predictors was obtained can be found
164 in the **Supplementary Methods 2**.

165 **Statistical analysis**

166 We applied multiple imputation to impute the missing values of candidate predictors, except child BMI
167 polygenic risk score (PRS). The detailed method for multiple imputation is described in the **Supplementary**
168 **Methods 3**. **Table S3** presents the percentage of missing values for each predictor, as well as the variables
169 used to impute these missing data.

Predictors of child BMI

170 We used the Deletion-Substitution-Addition (DSA) algorithm²⁷ to identify key predictors from candidate
171 predictors selected in evidence synthesis, and performed multiple linear regression model. The DSA
172 algorithm is an aggressive iterative model search and a loss-based cross-validated algorithm that works by
173 deleting a predictor, substituting one predictor by another, or adding a predictor to the model at each
174 iteration²⁸. At the end of each iteration, a final model is selected by minimizing the value of the root mean
175 squared error of prediction. It has been used in exposome studies²⁹, and has been shown to have a lower
176 false positive rate in comparison with other linear regression-based variable selection algorithms in a
177 simulation study³⁰. Repeating the predictor selection procedure with cross-validation can result in different
178 sets of predictors in the models. To get a stable predictor selection, we fitted 5-fold cross-validated DSA
179 50 times. We performed DSA on zBMI and weight status as outcomes separately. Predictors that were
180 retained in at least 10% of the DSA models were selected to fit final multiple linear regression models for
181 childhood BMI or logistic regression models for child weight status. The DSA was applied in stacked data
182 with 20 imputed datasets allowed up to 25 variables in the final model³¹.

183 After finalizing the list of key predictors, we applied multiple linear regression to fit prediction models for
184 child BMI, and logistic regression to model child weight status. All identified key predictors entered the
185 models simultaneously. Overall explained variance of the fitted linear regression models for childhood BMI
186 was quantified by the coefficient of determination (R^2). Explained variance of the fitted logistic regression
187 models for child weight status (overweight and obesity vs normal weight and underweight) was quantified
188 by McFadden's pseudo R^2 ³². We further quantified relative importance of the predictors by estimating the
189 decompositions of R^2 in linear regression with the “Lindeman, Merenda, and Gold” method³³ that are
190 implemented in the ‘relaimpo’ R package³⁴. This method proposed to average order-dependent allocation
191 overall ordering for a fair unique assessment of R^2 for each predictor. We estimated the relative importance
192 of the predictors in the logistic regression with the relative explained variation metric³⁵ that are implemented
193 in the ‘rms’ R package³⁶, which is an identical measure to relative R^2 if the original model was ordinary
194 least-square.

195 Before entering the algorithm, all continuous predictors were normalized by interquartile range (IQR). As
196 such, one unit increase in each predictor corresponds to an interquartile range change. We did not allow
197 interaction or non-linear terms in the DSA model search due to the concerns regarding statistical power
198 overload.

199 We performed several sensitivity analyses for models of childhood BMI and weight status. First, we added
200 child BMI PRS in the models to account for genetic influences. Second, the models were stratified by sex
201 to obtain sex-specific estimates. Third, the models were stratified by child ethnic background to obtain
202 ethnicity-specific estimates. Fourth, to explore more parsimonious models, we conducted an additional
203 model selection using DSA based on cross-validation risk estimates³⁷, which provide insights into model
204 sizes and complexity. Based on a visual inspection of cross-validation risk plots for child BMI and weight
205 status, we determined an optimal model size. Subsequently, we fitted parsimonious multiple regression
206 models. Last, to evaluate whether including all candidate predictors would increase the explained variance,
207 we conducted analyses using all candidate predictors in the models. All statistical analyses were performed
208 with R version 4.1.2 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

209 **Results**

210 **Results of the evidence synthesis**

211 **Figure 1** presents the study selection in the PRISMA flow chart. In total, 142 full-text articles were screened
212 based on the eligibility assessment. Among them, 49 studies were excluded because: (1) 29 studies did not
213 report BMI as an outcome; (2) 6 studies reported effect estimates for overweight and obesity only; (3) 3
214 studies did not provide sufficient information for effect estimates computation and conversion; (4) 3 studies
215 did not provide an individual effect for Generation R data; (5) 8 studies were conducted in sub-cohorts of
216 the study. In total, the selection yielded 93 studies that were conducted within the Generation R Study and
217 used children's BMI or zBMI as an outcome and met the inclusion criteria.

Predictors of child BMI

218 An overview of study characteristics is summarized in **Table S4**, along with its references (**Reference list**
219 **of publications included in the evidence synthesis**). In total, 210 predictors were reported in different
220 studies. Ages at assessment of the candidate predictors ranged from preconception to 10 years, and
221 children's age at BMI assessment ranged from 2 to 10 years. We illustrated the summary forest plots for
222 predictors with pooled effect sizes above the threshold $|d| \geq 0.1$ in **Figure S1**. Below we summarize the
223 results of the meta-analyses per domain.

224 *Sociodemographic predictors*

225 Sociodemographic predictors were reported in 11 studies, which together explored 5 predictors (**Table S5**).
226 Maternal education, assessed both during pregnancy and when children were 6 years old, had the largest
227 effect ($d = 0.57$) on child BMI at age 10 years, and paternal education, measured at the same time points,
228 had an effect size of $d = 0.39$. Child ethnicity was associated with child BMI at age 6 years with $d = 0.37$.

229 *Preconception and prenatal parental health*

230 Prenatal predictors were examined in 21 studies, which explored 22 predictors (**Table S6**). Maternal pre-
231 pregnancy weight, maternal and paternal pre-pregnancy BMI each had pooled effect sizes larger than $d =$
232 0.10 on child BMI at age 2 to 10 years, ranging from 0.10 to 0.31 . Maternal smoking assessed in three
233 trimesters of pregnancy ($d = 0.10$) and paternal smoking assessed in early pregnancy ($d = 0.13$) predicted
234 higher child BMI at 6 years. Maternal cannabis use ($d = 0.17$), and paternal cannabis ($d = 0.13$) and tobacco
235 use ($d = 0.13$), both assessed in early pregnancy, predicted higher child BMI at 10 years.

236 *Maternal nutritional predictors*

237 Maternal nutritional predictors were examined in 13 studies, which explored 31 predictors (**Table S7**).
238 Maternal vomiting during the first trimester had the largest effect ($d = 0.26$) on child BMI at age 6 years.
239 As for dietary intake during pregnancy, milk intake during early pregnancy ($d = 0.15$), plasma total n-6
240 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) concentration ($d = 0.11$) and higher adherence to a vegetable, fish, and

Predictors of child BMI

241 oil dietary pattern during pregnancy ($d = 0.10$) predicted higher child BMI at age 6. Plasma arachidonic
242 acid (AA) ($d = -0.11$) and docosatetraenoic acid (DTA) ($d = -0.10$) concentration predicted a lower child
243 BMI at age 2, and 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25(OH) D) ($d = -0.11$) concentration during pregnancy predicted
244 a lower child BMI at age 6 years. Children whose mothers started to use folic acid supplement
245 preconceptionally or in the first 10 weeks had lower BMI than those of mothers never used folic acid
246 supplement ($d = -0.11$).

247 *Genetic predictors*

248 Genetic predictors were examined in 7 studies, which explored 58 predictors (**Table S8**). The effect sizes
249 of 2 predictors were above the cut-off: rs7185735, a common single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) of
250 the fat mass and obesity-associated (FTO) gene ($d = 0.12$), and the hypothalamic expression and
251 regulation polygenetic risk score ($d = 0.10$), which is a weighted PRS of a subset of the SNPs identified to
252 be associated with BMI in adults that are annotated to genes with a potential role in these processes.

253 *Maternal mental health and parenting predictors*

254 Maternal mental health and parenting predictors were examined in 8 studies, which explored 14 predictors
255 (**Table S9**). Maternal psychopathology symptoms during pregnancy had the largest effect size ($d = 0.42$)
256 in its association with child BMI at age 10 years. Maternal postpartum depression also predicted a higher
257 child BMI at age 3 ($d = 0.13$). Breastfeeding duration, timing of first introduction of solid foods and
258 restrictive feeding practices at ages 4 and 10 years were linked to a higher child BMI at age 10 (d range
259 from 0.12 to 0.22), while the pressure to eat feeding practice at ages 2 and 4 years was associated with a
260 lower subsequent child BMI ($d = -0.12$ and -0.13 , for ages 4 and 6, respectively).

261 *Early-life weight and weight gain predictors*

262 Early-life weight and weight gain predictors were examined in 7 studies, which explored 17 predictors
263 (**Table S10**). For child anthropometrics, BMI at 1.5 months and 2 years, and BMI change across infancy

Predictors of child BMI

264 (6-24 months) were associated with a higher child BMI at 6 years ($d = 0.22, 0.58, 0.16$, respectively). Higher
265 central-to-total fat mass ratio and total subcutaneous fat mass in infancy were also related to higher child
266 BMI at 6 years. For child growth patterns, higher weight gain during infancy (0-24 months), small-for-
267 gestational-age combined with catch up growth or large-for-gestational-age combined without catch down
268 growth (0-24 months), higher peak weight velocity (1-36 months), and higher BMI at estimated adiposity
269 peak were associated with a higher subsequent child BMI at 4 or 6 years of age (d range from 0.12 to 0.58).
270 Fetal growth restriction was associated with a lower child BMI at age 6 ($d = -0.79$).

271 *Infant and childhood nutritional predictors*

272 Infant and childhood nutritional predictors were examined in 9 studies, which explored 24 predictors (**Table**
273 **S11**). Higher adherence to fat mass index and fat-free mass index derived dietary pattern ($d = 0.14$) during
274 infancy predicted a higher child BMI at 6 years of age. Higher relative intake of animal proteins ($d = 0.13$)
275 or plant proteins ($d = 0.14$) during infancy predicted a higher child BMI at age 10, and.

276 *Child behavioral predictors*

277 Child behavioral predictors were examined in 14 studies, which examined 26 predictors (**Table S12**).
278 Among eating behaviors, breakfast skipping ($d = 0.32$) and lunch skipping ($d = 0.19$) at ages 4 and 6 years
279 had the largest effect sizes on BMI at age 6. These were followed by eating behavior sub-scales assessed at
280 4 and 10 years, which were associated with concurrent or subsequent child BMI. The sub-scales included
281 emotional overeating, emotional undereating, enjoyment of food, food responsiveness, and satiety
282 responsiveness, with d ranging from -0.10 for emotional undereating to 0.26 for food responsiveness.
283 Among sedentary behavior and physical activity, TV viewing ($d = 0.19$), computer gaming ($d = 0.12$), and
284 outdoor playing ($d = 0.12$) assessed at age 6 years were associated with BMI at the same age. Better set-
285 shifting ability at age 4 years was associated with lower child BMI at 10 years ($d = -0.35$).

286 *Biological predictors*

287 In 2 studies, 3 biological predictors were reported (**Table S13**). Among them, child cortisone concentration
288 ($d = 0.23$) at age 6 years was associated with higher child BMI at 6 years, and child cortisol concentration
289 at age 6 years was associated with higher child BMI at both 6 years ($d = 0.6$) and 10 years ($d = 0.7$).

290 **Results of the prediction models**

291 Among predictors for which the association with child BMI reflected an effect size of $|d| \geq 0.1$, we selected
292 59 candidate predictors for prediction model building. The decision was made depending on the feasibility
293 of data collection in the real-world setting (e.g., peak weight velocity was estimated, thus was not selected).
294 When faced with several composite measurements of molecular predictors, we chose aggregated
295 measurements. For instance, considering AA and DTA as components of total n-6 PUFA, only the total n-
296 6 PUFA was considered for inclusion. As for predictors in the genetic domain, we replaced them with child
297 BMI PRS which was constructed using identified genetic loci associated with childhood BMI in a large
298 consortium study. The 59 candidate predictors are categorized into 9 domains (**Table 1**).

299 Of 5686 children included, 50.4% was girls, 60.1% had a Dutch ethnic background, and 18.0% had
300 overweight or obesity (**Table 2**). More than half of the parents were highly educated (university degree) in
301 this study population (**Table S14**). The interquartile range of all candidate predictors, used as the reference
302 unit of change in the multiple regression analysis, is reported in **Table S14**. Out of the 59 candidate
303 predictors, the final multi-predictor DSA models of z BMI selected 25 key predictors (**Table 3**, z BMI),
304 including child ethnicity, both parents' education and BMI, maternal smoking during pregnancy, vitamin
305 D concentration during pregnancy, folic acid supplement use, milk intake during pregnancy, mother's
306 feeding practices (pressure to eat and restriction), early-life weight characteristics (child weight gain and
307 BMI during infancy), high fat mass dietary pattern and protein intake at age 1, and child behaviors
308 (enjoyment of food, food responsiveness, satiety responsiveness, breakfast skipping and set-shifting).
309 Altogether, these key predictors explained 49.2% (95%CI: 47.0%, 51.4%) of the variance in z BMI at age
310 10. The decomposition of R^2 shows that key predictors in preconception and prenatal parental health (8.9%),

Predictors of child BMI

311 early-life weight and weight gain (20.2%), and child behavior (10.5%) domains accounted for the largest
312 proportions of explained variance in mid-childhood zBMI (**Figure 2**), with maternal prepregnancy BMI,
313 paternal BMI, child zBMI at age 2, BMI at adiposity peak, food responsiveness and satiety responsiveness
314 at age 10 each constituting a substantial portion within their respective domains.

315 The final multi-predictor DSA models of overweight and obesity selected 25 key predictors (**Table 3**,
316 overweight and obesity). Among them, 20 predictors (~80%) overlap with those selected from DSA models
317 of zBMI. In addition to these overlapping predictors, the models selected maternal total n-6 PUFA status
318 during pregnancy, the timing of the introduction of solid foods, breastfeeding duration, emotional
319 overeating at age 10 years, and outdoor play. The key predictors combined explained 33.7% variance in the
320 odds of having overweight or obesity at age 10 years. **Figure 3** illustrates the relative explained variance
321 by each predictor of childhood overweight and obesity, with predictors in the preconception and prenatal
322 parental health (5.8%), early-life weight and weight gain (9.5%), and child behavior (11.1%) domains
323 constituting the largest proportions. Within these domains, maternal prepregnancy BMI, paternal BMI,
324 child BMI at age 2, food responsiveness and satiety responsiveness at age 10 accounted for substantial
325 proportions.

326 Adding child BMI PRS to the main models does not substantially change effect estimates or R^2 (**Table S15**):
327 the explained variance in zBMI is 48.7% (95%CI: 46.1%, 51.2%) when adding the child BMI PRS and
328 additionally adjusted for four genetic ancestry principal components in the model. In the model of
329 overweight and obesity, the explained variance slightly increased to 35.2% when additionally adding child
330 BMI PRS. Effect estimates were similar when stratified by child sex (**Table S16**) and ethnic backgrounds
331 (**Table S17**). After examining the cross-validation risk plots for child zBMI (**Figure S2, A**) and weight
332 status (**Figure S2, B**), we determined an optimal maximum model size of 10 predictors for each model and
333 conducted multiple regression analyses in a parsimonious way. The 10 selected key predictors (**Table S18**)
334 align with those that accounted for the largest proportions in the main models. While comparisons between
335 these parsimonious models and the main models indicate that the main models are preferred ($p < 0.001$), the

336 explained variance by 10 predictors in the parsimonious models (46.4% for zBMI and 31.3% for overweight
337 and obesity) suggests a comparable fit to the main models. Finally, in the models with 59 candidate
338 predictors, the overall explained variance is 42.9% (95%CI: 40.3%, 45.6%) for child BMI and 35.5% for
339 the odds of overweight and obesity (data not shown).

340 **Discussion**

341 This study used systematic analytic strategies to synthesize and analyze predictors of BMI in mid-childhood
342 from preconception parental health and subsequent fetal and child development onwards, with the goal of
343 identifying salient predictors. Out of 210 predictors examined by studies conducted using the Generation R
344 Study data, we identified 59 candidate predictors, from which 32 were identified as independent key
345 predictors of either child zBMI or weight status at age 10 years by the DSA model search algorithm. These
346 key predictors included: child's ethnic background, and parental educational levels in the *sociodemographic*
347 domain; parental BMI before pregnancy, and mother's smoking status during pregnancy in the
348 *preconception and prenatal parental health* domain; mother's total n-6 PUFA status, blood concentration
349 of vitamin D, folic acid supplement use, and milk consumption in the *maternal nutrition during pregnancy*
350 domain; the timing of the introduction of solid foods, breastfeeding duration, and mother's regulation of
351 child food intake in the *maternal mental health and parenting* domain; weight gain and BMI during infancy
352 in the *early-life weight* domain; adherence to a high fat-mass dietary pattern and protein intake during
353 infancy in the *infant and childhood nutrition* domain; enjoyment of food, emotional overeating, food
354 responsiveness, satiety responsiveness, breakfast skipping, television viewing, outdoor play, and higher set-
355 shifting abilities in the *child behavior* domain. In total, these identified key predictors accounted for
356 approximately 49.2% of the variance in zBMI and 33.7% of the variance in the odds of having overweight
357 or obesity at the age of 10 years.

358 *Strongest predictors in prenatal, early-life weight and child behavior domains*

Predictors of child BMI

359 To our knowledge, this is the first study to elucidate the contributions of a wide range of predictors
360 simultaneously for childhood BMI. Our study contributes to prioritizing key predictors that explain the
361 variability of child BMI by decomposing the explained variance. We pinpointed predictors across three
362 domains—early-life weight, child behaviors, and preconception and prenatal parental health—that
363 accounted for the largest proportions of explained variance in BMI and weight status.

364 Within the early-life weight domain, infant weight gain, and BMI across infancy are the strongest predictors,
365 accounting for the largest fraction of the variability in child zBMI at age 10 years, namely 20.2%. Rapid
366 weight gain in infancy has consistently been linked to risk of later childhood obesity and has been used in
367 prediction models. One meta-analysis reported that rapid weight gain during the first 2 years of life (defined
368 as >0.67 weight gain z-score) was associated with 4.16 times greater odds of having overweight or obesity
369 in childhood³⁸. Our results on absolute weight gain at three time points during infancy are in line with this
370 finding, although the effect estimates are not directly comparable. BMI at single time points during infancy,
371 at age 2 years and at estimated adiposity peak were also identified as key predictors, in accordance with
372 previous studies reporting strong tracking of early-childhood BMI into adolescence³. A study comparing
373 BMI and infant weight gain suggested a simple measure of weight status at a single time point between 6
374 and 24 months of age to be a stronger risk factor for later obesity and may have more clinical utility and
375 accuracy than weight gain³⁹. In a study tracking the course of BMI over time in over 50,000 children in
376 Germany, adolescents with overweight and obesity had higher mean BMI z-scores starting at age 1 year,
377 and had the greatest annual increase in BMI z-score between ages 2 and 6 years³, which was suggested to
378 be a feature of early adiposity rebound⁴⁰. Considering that early adiposity rebound can only be observed
379 retrospectively, a higher BMI at age 2 years may be a more feasible indicator for future upward deviation
380 in BMI percentile and a useful measure for population-based prevention of obesity.

381 Within the child behavior domain, food responsiveness and satiety responsiveness emerged as the strongest
382 predictors, collectively constituting the largest fraction of the variance of the odds of having overweight
383 and obesity at the age of 10 years (9.5%) and the second largest fraction of the variability in child zBMI at

Predictors of child BMI

384 age 10 years (10.2%). Notably, to our knowledge, these predictors have not been previously integrated into
385 prediction models, despite numerous observational studies reporting a consistent association with BMI in
386 childhood. In a recent meta-analysis, pooled effect estimates of food responsiveness on zBMI was
387 comparable to our finding, while our effect estimate of satiety responsiveness was somewhat smaller⁴¹. One
388 explanation could be that we included early-life weight gain in the model, which has been found to predict
389 decreased satiety responsiveness at age 5 years⁴², but is not commonly controlled in previous studies.
390 Longitudinal assessments of these eating behaviors revealed a moderate stability of both food
391 responsiveness and satiety responsiveness in children aged 2 to 11 years⁴³⁻⁴⁵. Moreover, bidirectional
392 associations between these eating behaviors and BMI have also been observed in children older than 4 years
393 of age in a few longitudinal studies⁴¹. Considering that food responsiveness and satiety responsiveness
394 measured at age 10 years were selected in the model, we reckon that they may be (partly) the consequence
395 of higher BMI prior to mid-childhood.

396 Within the preconception and prenatal parental health domain, parental BMI before pregnancy was a critical
397 predictor which stands as the third largest part of the variability in mid-childhood zBMI. Parental BMI is
398 the most used determinant in prediction modeling and appears to be an important predictor in studies
399 examining obesity in mid-childhood⁴⁶. Familial aggregation of obesity is well-documented; parents provide
400 both genes and obesogenic family environment that can promote childhood obesity in susceptible
401 individuals. Recent meta-analyses quantified the effect sizes of these relationships. For example, an
402 individual participant data meta-analysis using data from 162,129 mother-child pairs across 37 cohort
403 studies, including the Generation R Study, underscored the impact of maternal pre-pregnancy BMI on child
404 BMI, particularly in late childhood (10-18 years)⁴⁷. Another meta-analysis highlighted a positive
405 association in children aged between 1 and 14 years, reporting a 264% increase in the odds of child obesity
406 when mothers have obesity before conception⁴⁸. Paternal pre-pregnancy BMI, although less studied, also
407 showed considerable associations with offspring BMI, possibly with a greater impact from mid-childhood
408 onward⁴⁹. Two reviews compared the magnitude of mother-child and father-child BMI associations^{50, 51}.

Predictors of child BMI

409 Together, these studies suggest that there is no consistent pattern until mid-adolescence, but thereafter, the
410 magnitude of associations of parental BMI with offspring BMI were similar for both parents (around 0.23
411 per SD increase in maternal or paternal BMI). Our results are in line with these estimated magnitudes.
412 Collectively, these findings emphasize an equal importance between maternal and paternal (pre-pregnancy)
413 BMI in predicting offspring adiposity measures from mid-childhood onwards.

414 *Explained proportions of the variability in mid-childhood BMI and weight status*

415 Our study reveals a remarkable proportion of explained variance in mid-childhood zBMI and weight status:
416 with the large number of predictors studied, approximately half of the variability in BMI was explained.
417 This finding underscores the multifaceted nature of obesity in childhood, which has been widely
418 acknowledged to have both gene-environment causes, which may also interact.

419 Notably, the strongest predictors found in this study appeared to be precursing or mediating phenotypes
420 that have some genetic underpinnings and may reflect such complex interplay. In light of this, our identified
421 proportion of the explained variance warrants interpretation within the context of the heritability of child
422 BMI. Narrow-sense heritability (h^2) has been used to quantify the proportion of variance attributable to the
423 additive genetic variation, which is equivalent to the R^2 in a linear regression model in which additive
424 genetic variation is regressed on BMI. A study including 45 twin studies found that the h^2 of BMI increased
425 with age, ranging from 42-84%, and the h^2 reached its highest estimate (around 80%) for both boys and
426 girls around mid-childhood⁵². Most, if not all, of the individual-level key predictors selected in this study
427 are heritable. For example, estimated h^2 for food responsiveness and satiety responsiveness was around
428 70%^{53, 54}. Moreover, family-level key predictors, including parental BMI, can have a strong influence
429 through inheritance. In this study, we included PRS of child BMI in the models, which captures part of the
430 additive genetic variation. However, the inclusion of BMI PRS did not substantially change the explained
431 variance in child BMI or weight status. This is not surprising, considering that as observed in a previous
432 study⁵⁵, the 25-loci combined PRS accounted for merely 3.6% of the variability in childhood BMI at 10

433 years. These findings fit the observation that the combination of common variants typically only explain
434 small fractions of trait variance⁵⁶. Indeed, a recent PRS study based on 2.1 million common SNPs explained
435 only 8.4% of the variation in BMI⁵⁷. Moreover, we included predictors that are presumably on the pathways
436 of genes to BMI, diluting the effect of PRS to a great extent. On the other hand, this suggests that we may
437 already capture a considerable part of the genetic variation with phenotypical predictors.

438 The significant role of genetic factors in BMI does not downplay the importance of environmental factors
439 associated with childhood obesity, because genetic factors can affect BMI by modifying food intake and
440 behavioral factors. Importantly, shared and unique environmental factors explain at least 20% of the
441 variability of BMI throughout childhood⁵². Our estimated explained variance of BMI likely encompasses a
442 substantial part of both genetic variance, environmental variance, and their covariance. However, a notable
443 missing proportion of explained variance of mid-childhood BMI remains. Factors from psychosocial,
444 cultural, broader environmental and macro-system domains not addressed in this study, such as childhood
445 adverse experiences⁵⁸, cultural beliefs⁵⁹, food environment⁶⁰, food marketing⁶¹, air pollution⁶², built
446 environment⁶³, early child care environment⁶⁴, and utilization of perinatal services⁶⁵, have all been
447 associated with BMI trajectories and the development of obesity in childhood in other work, but were not
448 (yet) addressed in the Generation R Study. For genetic variance, missing heritability suggests that additional
449 genetic loci (including low/rare frequency alleles), or other genetic variants such as copy number variations
450 predisposing to BMI and overweight or obesity remain to be discovered. Epigenetic mechanisms may be
451 another source of missing variance, as it has shown additive explanatory capacity to health outcomes
452 beyond genetic predictors⁶⁶ and partially captured environmental effect⁶⁷. Moreover, integrated multi-omics
453 approaches, which include downstream physiological response to the interaction between genes and
454 environment, also hold the potential to fill in a fraction of the missing proportions of the variability in mid-
455 childhood BMI. While understanding how the environment interacts with a genetic predisposition to obesity
456 is challenging to achieve soon, future studies should also focus on investigating modifiable causal factors.

Predictors of child BMI

457 The key predictors identified in the current study have potential for substantial effects but randomized
458 controlled trials are needed to establish causality and modifiability in practice.

459 *Strengths and limitations*

460 Major strengths of this study are the utilization of domain-related knowledge generated from a large
461 pediatric population-based prospective study, and the inclusion of a wide range of predictors of childhood
462 obesity, covering factors across preconception to mid-childhood. We pre-selected predictors in an evidence-
463 based manner, taking prior knowledge into account before building prediction models. This approach would
464 potentially improve the interpretability of prediction models. Furthermore, we used a model search
465 algorithm with cross-validation to select the ‘best bet’ list of important predictors. We identified novel
466 predictors, such as eating behaviors, as key predictors which often not included in previous prediction
467 modeling studies. Moreover, we identified the proportion of variability in mid-childhood BMI that still
468 cannot be explained.

469 Our results should be interpreted in the context of several limitations. First, the study was conducted in one
470 cohort study in the Netherlands; thus, the results are population-specific and prone to overfitting. The
471 generalizability of the findings needs to be established. Predictors selected by meta-analysis but not by DSA
472 could still be important to predict child BMI in other settings. Therefore, replication is needed in other
473 cohorts with data collected from a life course perspective. Second, limitations associated with using zBMI
474 scores should be acknowledged. The reference population for the Dutch growth chart included only children
475 with at least one parent of Dutch origin. Consequently, applying this chart to standardize BMI in children
476 from non-Dutch or mixed backgrounds could introduce bias. However, sensitivity analyses stratified by
477 ethnic background showed similar estimates for children with Dutch and non-Dutch backgrounds,
478 supporting the robustness of the key predictors identified in this study. Additionally, zBMI shows a reduced
479 ability to distinguish among children with severe obesity due to the “ceiling effect”. This effect arises from
480 restricted zBMI variance above the 97th percentile due to sparse reference data, which was observed in other

Predictors of child BMI

481 growth references using the LMS method, such as the 2000 CDC growth chart⁶⁸. This limitation may
482 influence the generalizability of our findings to children at the more extreme end of the BMI spectrum.
483 Third, interactions between two or more variables may account for additional explained variance of BMI
484 or weight status, which were not examined in this study, as potential synergistic effects among predictors
485 may have a stronger influence on BMI or weight status than their combined additive effect. Indeed, a few
486 previous studies included in our evidence synthesis reported interactions between some predictors and sex
487 or child ethnic background⁶⁹⁻⁷². However, due to constraints of statistical power, we did not formally
488 examine these interactions in the main models, and instead presented stratified results as sensitivity analysis.
489 Fourth, we cannot infer causality from the results because of the exploratory and correlational nature of our
490 prediction model. Fifth, we cannot rule out the potential contribution of predictors that were not selected
491 by the DSA algorithm in the variability of mid-childhood BMI, despite that they may have relatively small
492 effect sizes and may not be independently associated with BMI in mid-childhood in the current study. Those
493 predictors might still be of interest in terms of prevention and intervention because they may be on the
494 pathway of selected predictors to child BMI, for example, as precursors, mediators or effect modifiers.

495 Some conceptionally important predictors were not selected, for example, diet in childhood. Nevertheless,
496 our results do not downplay those predictors because they are associated with the identified key predictors
497 in the current study to a varying degree. Instead, future studies may take the key predictors we identified as
498 a starting point to investigate the underlying causal mechanism of childhood obesity in experimental studies.

499 Last, data on some biological factors and environmental factor (i.e. immune biomarkers, taste preference,
500 sleep, 24-hour activity rhythms, air pollution, and endocrine disrupting chemicals) was only available in
501 sub-cohorts⁷³⁻⁷⁸, therefore not included in this study. Data on community-level factors (e.g., policy-related
502 predictors) were not reported in the published studies of Generation R. Those potential predictors need
503 attention in large-scale studies across countries in the future.

504 **Conclusion**

505 We found that mid-childhood BMI and weight status were associated with multiple predictors in
506 multifaceted domains, particularly those related to preconception and prenatal parental health, early-life
507 weight, and child behaviors. We observed predictors spanning various aspects of children's development
508 and their environments explain a larger proportion of the variance in BMI and weight status than any
509 previous study. Nevertheless, the large gap of unexplained variance suggests that some uncharted predictors
510 need to be uncovered or that 'main effects are in the interactions'⁷⁹. The results set a stage for future research
511 to understand how those predictors jointly mediate the influence of the obesogenic environment on child
512 BMI. Although more experimental intervention studies are needed to establish causality, we speculate that
513 multimodal interventions early in the life cycle are potentially the most effective in maintaining a healthy
514 weight along the life course. Our sensitivity analysis, using a parsimonious model with 10 key predictors
515 primarily clustered in the three domains mentioned above, demonstrated a comparable fit to our main model.
516 Future predictive and interventional studies are encouraged to test and validate these 10 key predictors for
517 utilization in practical settings. Likely, such interventions target factors that affect parental BMI in the pre-
518 conception phase and during pregnancy, as well as managing appetite and preventing early adiposity
519 rebound are the most impactful. Early life preventive efforts, starting as early as preconception stages, are
520 crucial for supporting parents and children in adopting healthy behaviors and maintaining a healthy weight.
521 Recent developed prevention programs for adults planning to have children have shown promising effects
522 with the adoption of positive health behaviors and weight management⁸⁰. Whether the reported effects on
523 adults' lifestyle and weight also translate to offspring's health behaviors that carry over into later life by
524 reducing obesity risk needs to be shown in the future.

525 **Author contributions**

526 Yuchan Mou (conceptualization, data screening, data extraction, data curation, statistical analysis, writing
527 – original draft, writing – review and editing), Susana Santos (consultation of statistical analysis, writing –

528 review and editing), Macarena Lara (data screening, data extraction, writing – review and editing), Ivonne
529 P.M. Derks (data extraction, writing – review and editing), Vincent W.V. Jaddoe (resources, writing –
530 review and editing), Romy Gaillard (resources, writing – review and editing), Janine F. Felix (resources,
531 writing – review and editing), Eric Steegers (resources, writing – review and editing), Trudy Voortman
532 (data screening, data extraction, resources, writing – review and editing), Marinus H. van IJzendoorn
533 (conceptualization, data screening, data extraction, consultation of statistical analysis, writing – review and
534 editing), Pauline W. Jansen (conceptualization, resources, data screening, data extraction, supervision,
535 writing – review and editing). Yuchan Mou and Pauline W. Jansen had primary responsibility for final
536 content. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

537 **Acknowledgements**

538 The Generation R Study is conducted by Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, in close
539 collaboration with the School of Law and the Faculty of Social Sciences at the Erasmus University,
540 Rotterdam; the Municipal Health Service, Rotterdam area; and the Stichting Trombosedienst &
541 Artsenlaboratorium Rijnmond (Star-MDC), Rotterdam. We gratefully acknowledge the contribution of
542 mothers, general practitioners, hospitals, midwives, and pharmacies in Rotterdam, the Netherlands. We
543 would also like to thank Xinglan Shi for crafting the figures in this study.

544 **Data accessibility**

545 Data described in the predictive modeling part cannot be made publicly available because of confidentiality,
546 but data can be requested and shared with a formal data-sharing agreement. Requests for data, code book,
547 and analytic code can be directed to datamangementenr@erasmusmc.nl.

548 **References**

- 549 1 Collaboration NRF. Worldwide trends in body-mass index, underweight, overweight, and obesity
550 from 1975 to 2016: a pooled analysis of 2416 population-based measurement studies in 128.9 million
551 children, adolescents, and adults. *Lancet*. 2017; 390: 2627-42.
- 552 2 Ward ZJ, Long MW, Resch SC, et al. Simulation of Growth Trajectories of Childhood Obesity into
553 Adulthood. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2017; 377: 2145-53.
- 554 3 Geserick M, Vogel M, Gausche R, et al. Acceleration of BMI in Early Childhood and Risk of
555 Sustained Obesity. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2018; 379: 1303-12.
- 556 4 Quek YH, Tam WWS, Zhang MWB, Ho RCM. Exploring the association between childhood and
557 adolescent obesity and depression: a meta-analysis. *Obes Rev*. 2017; 18: 742-54.
- 558 5 Cortese S, Ferrin M, Brandeis D, et al. Cognitive training for attention-deficit/hyperactivity
559 disorder: meta-analysis of clinical and neuropsychological outcomes from randomized controlled trials. *J*
560 *Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry*. 2015; 54: 164-74.
- 561 6 Juonala M, Magnussen CG, Berenson GS, et al. Childhood Adiposity, Adult Adiposity, and
562 Cardiovascular Risk Factors. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2011; 365: 1876-85.
- 563 7 Franks PW, Hanson RL, Knowler WC, et al. Childhood Obesity, Other Cardiovascular Risk Factors,
564 and Premature Death. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2010; 362: 485-93.
- 565 8 Reilly JJ, Kelly J. Long-term impact of overweight and obesity in childhood and adolescence on
566 morbidity and premature mortality in adulthood: systematic review. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2011; 35: 891-8.
- 567 9 Han JC, Lawlor DA, Kimm SYS. Childhood obesity. *The Lancet*. 2010; 375: 1737-48.
- 568 10 D'Souza NJ, Kuswara K, Zheng M, et al. A systematic review of lifestyle patterns and their
569 association with adiposity in children aged 5–12 years. *Obesity Reviews*. 2020; 21: e13029.
- 570 11 Mead E, Brown T, Rees K, et al. Diet, physical activity and behavioural interventions for the
571 treatment of overweight or obese children from the age of 6 to 11 years. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*.
572 2017; 6: Cd012651.
- 573 12 Vrijheid M, Fossati S, Maitre L, et al. Early-Life Environmental Exposures and Childhood Obesity:
574 An Exposome-Wide Approach. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2020; 128: 67009.
- 575 13 Craigie AM, Lake AA, Kelly SA, Adamson AJ, Mathers JC. Tracking of obesity-related behaviours
576 from childhood to adulthood: A systematic review. *Maturitas*. 2011; 70: 266-84.
- 577 14 Simmonds M, Llewellyn A, Owen CG, Woolacott N. Predicting adult obesity from childhood
578 obesity: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obesity Reviews*. 2016; 17: 95-107.
- 579 15 Skinner AC, Perrin EM, Moss LA, Skelton JA. Cardiometabolic Risks and Severity of Obesity in
580 Children and Young Adults. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2015; 373: 1307-17.
- 581 16 Kelly Y, Patalay P, Montgomery S, Sacker A. BMI Development and Early Adolescent Psychosocial
582 Well-Being: UK Millennium Cohort Study. *Pediatrics*. 2016; 138.
- 583 17 Kooijman MN, Kruithof CJ, van Duijn CM, et al. The Generation R Study: design and cohort
584 update 2017. *European Journal of Epidemiology*. 2016; 31: 1243-64.
- 585 18 Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for
586 reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*. 2021; 372: n71.
- 587 19 Higgins JPT, Eldridge S, Li T. Chapter 23: Including variants on randomized trials. In: Higgins JPT,
588 Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, et al. (eds.). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic*
589 *Reviews of Interventions version 63 (updated February 2022)*. Cochrane 2022.
- 590 20 Lüdecke D, Lüdecke MD, Calculator'from David BW. Package 'esc'. *R Package Version 05*. 2019;
591 1: 2019.
- 592 21 Lipsey MW, Wilson DB. *Practical meta-analysis*: SAGE publications, Inc 2001.

- 593 22 Wan X, Wang W, Liu J, Tong T. Estimating the sample mean and standard deviation from the
594 sample size, median, range and/or interquartile range. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*. 2014; 14:
595 135.
- 596 23 Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch V. Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of
597 interventions. *Hoboken: Wiley*. 2019.
- 598 24 Borenstein M, Hedges LV, Higgins JP, Rothstein HR. A basic introduction to fixed-effect and
599 random-effects models for meta-analysis. *Res Synth Methods*. 2010; 1: 97-111.
- 600 25 Fredriks AM, van Buuren S, Wit JM, Verloove-Vanhorick SP. Body index measurements in 1996-7
601 compared with 1980. *Arch Dis Child*. 2000; 82: 107-12.
- 602 26 Cole TJ, Bellizzi MC, Flegal KM, Dietz WH. Establishing a standard definition for child overweight
603 and obesity worldwide: international survey. *Bmj*. 2000; 320: 1240.
- 604 27 Sinisi SE, Laan MJvd. Deletion/Substitution/Addition Algorithm in Learning with Applications in
605 Genomics. *Statistical Applications in Genetics and Molecular Biology*. 2004; 3.
- 606 28 Santos S, Maitre L, Warembourg C, et al. Applying the exposome concept in birth cohort
607 research: a review of statistical approaches. *European Journal of Epidemiology*. 2020; 35: 193-204.
- 608 29 Vrijheid M, Fossati S, Maitre L, et al. Early-Life Environmental Exposures and Childhood Obesity:
609 An Exposome-Wide Approach. *Environmental Health Perspectives*. 2020; 128: 067009.
- 610 30 Agier L, Portengen L, Chadeau-Hyam M, et al. A Systematic Comparison of Linear Regression–
611 Based Statistical Methods to Assess Exposome-Health Associations. *Environmental Health Perspectives*.
612 2016; 124: 1848-56.
- 613 31 Wood AM, White IR, Royston P. How should variable selection be performed with multiply
614 imputed data? *Statistics in Medicine*. 2008; 27: 3227-46.
- 615 32 McFadden D. Quantitative methods for analysing travel behaviour of individuals: some recent
616 developments. In: Hensher DA, Stopher PR (eds.). *Behavioural travel modelling*. London: Croom Helm
617 1979; 279-318.
- 618 33 Lindeman RH, Merenda PF, Gold RZ. Introduction to bivariate and multivariate analysis. (*No*
619 *Title*). 1980.
- 620 34 Groemping U. Relative Importance for Linear Regression in R: The Package relaimpo. *Journal of*
621 *Statistical Software*. 2006; 17: 1 - 27.
- 622 35 Luchman JN. Relative Importance Analysis With Multicategory Dependent Variables::An
623 Extension and Review of Best Practices. *Organizational Research Methods*. 2014; 17: 452-71.
- 624 36 FE HJ. rms: Regression Modeling Strategies. 2023; R package version 6.8-0.
- 625 37 Haight TJ, Wang Y, van der Laan MJ, Tager IB. A cross-validation deletion-substitution-addition
626 model selection algorithm: Application to marginal structural models. *Comput Stat Data Anal*. 2010; 54:
627 3080-94.
- 628 38 Zheng M, Lamb KE, Grimes C, et al. Rapid weight gain during infancy and subsequent adiposity: a
629 systematic review and meta-analysis of evidence. *Obesity Reviews*. 2018; 19: 321-32.
- 630 39 Taylor RW, Haszard JJ, Meredith-Jones KA, et al. Rapid infant weight gain or point-in-time weight
631 status: Which is the best predictor of later obesity and body composition? *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2023;
632 31: 2583-92.
- 633 40 Koyama S, Ichikawa G, Kojima M, et al. Adiposity Rebound and the Development of Metabolic
634 Syndrome. *Pediatrics*. 2014; 133: e114-e19.
- 635 41 Kininmonth A, Smith A, Carnell S, et al. The association between childhood adiposity and
636 appetite assessed using the Child Eating Behavior Questionnaire and Baby Eating Behavior
637 Questionnaire: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obesity Reviews*. 2021; 22: e13169.
- 638 42 van Deutekom AW, Chinapaw MJM, Vrijkotte TGM, Gemke RBJ. The association of birth weight
639 and postnatal growth with energy intake and eating behavior at 5 years of age – a birth cohort study.
640 *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*. 2016; 13: 15.

- 641 43 Ashcroft J, Semmler C, Carnell S, van Jaarsveld CHM, Wardle J. Continuity and stability of eating
642 behaviour traits in children. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*. 2008; 62: 985-90.
- 643 44 Jansen E, Williams KE, Mallan KM, Nicholson JM, Daniels LA. Bidirectional associations between
644 mothers' feeding practices and child eating behaviours. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and*
645 *Physical Activity*. 2018; 15: 3.
- 646 45 Derks IPM, Bolhuis K, Sijbrands EJG, et al. Predictors and patterns of eating behaviors across
647 childhood: Results from The Generation R study. *Appetite*. 2019; 141: 104295.
- 648 46 LeCroy MN, Kim RS, Stevens J, Hanna DB, Isasi CR. Identifying Key Determinants of Childhood
649 Obesity: A Narrative Review of Machine Learning Studies. *Child Obes*. 2021; 17: 153-59.
- 650 47 Voerman E, Santos S, Patro Golab B, et al. Maternal body mass index, gestational weight gain,
651 and the risk of overweight and obesity across childhood: An individual participant data meta-analysis.
652 *PLoS Med*. 2019; 16: e1002744.
- 653 48 Heslehurst N, Vieira R, Akhter Z, et al. The association between maternal body mass index and
654 child obesity: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS Med*. 2019; 16: e1002817.
- 655 49 Zalbahar N, Najman J, McIntyre HD, Mamun A. Parental pre-pregnancy obesity and the risk of
656 offspring weight and body mass index change from childhood to adulthood. *Clin Obes*. 2017; 7: 206-15.
- 657 50 Patro B, Liber A, Zalewski B, et al. Maternal and paternal body mass index and offspring obesity:
658 a systematic review. *Ann Nutr Metab*. 2013; 63: 32-41.
- 659 51 Zhang J, Clayton GL, Overvad K, et al. Body mass index in parents and their adult offspring: A
660 systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obes Rev*. 2024; 25: e13644.
- 661 52 Silventoinen K, Jelenkovic A, Sund R, et al. Genetic and environmental effects on body mass
662 index from infancy to the onset of adulthood: an individual-based pooled analysis of 45 twin cohorts
663 participating in the COllaborative project of Development of Anthropometrical measures in Twins
664 (CODATwins) study1, 2, 3. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*. 2016; 104: 371-79.
- 665 53 Carnell S, Haworth CM, Plomin R, Wardle J. Genetic influence on appetite in children. *Int J Obes*
666 *(Lond)*. 2008; 32: 1468-73.
- 667 54 Llewellyn CH, van Jaarsveld CH, Johnson L, Carnell S, Wardle J. Nature and nurture in infant
668 appetite: analysis of the Gemini twin birth cohort. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2010; 91: 1172-9.
- 669 55 Vogelesang S, Bradfield JP, Ahluwalia TS, et al. Novel loci for childhood body mass index and
670 shared heritability with adult cardiometabolic traits. *PLOS Genetics*. 2020; 16: e1008718.
- 671 56 Loos RJF, Yeo GSH. The genetics of obesity: from discovery to biology. *Nature Reviews Genetics*.
672 2022; 23: 120-33.
- 673 57 Khera AV, Chaffin M, Wade KH, et al. Polygenic Prediction of Weight and Obesity Trajectories
674 from Birth to Adulthood. *Cell*. 2019; 177: 587-96.e9.
- 675 58 Danese A, Tan M. Childhood maltreatment and obesity: systematic review and meta-analysis.
676 *Molecular Psychiatry*. 2014; 19: 544-54.
- 677 59 Caprio S, Daniels SR, Drewnowski A, et al. Influence of race, ethnicity, and culture on childhood
678 obesity: implications for prevention and treatment: a consensus statement of Shaping America's Health
679 and the Obesity Society. *Diabetes care*. 2008; 31: 2211.
- 680 60 Jia P, Luo M, Li Y, et al. Fast - food restaurant, unhealthy eating, and childhood obesity: a
681 systematic review and meta - analysis. *Obesity Reviews*. 2021; 22: e12944.
- 682 61 Sadeghirad B, Duhaney T, Motaghipisheh S, Campbell NR, Johnston BC. Influence of unhealthy
683 food and beverage marketing on children's dietary intake and preference: a systematic review and
684 meta - analysis of randomized trials. *Obesity reviews*. 2016; 17: 945-59.
- 685 62 Nguyen Thi Khanh H, Rigau-Sabadell M, Khomenko S, et al. Ambient air pollution, urban green
686 space and childhood overweight and obesity: A health impact assessment for Barcelona, Spain.
687 *Environmental Research*. 2025; 264: 120306.

- 688 63 Malacarne D, Handakas E, Robinson O, et al. The built environment as determinant of childhood
689 obesity: A systematic literature review. *Obesity Reviews*. 2022; 23: e13385.
- 690 64 Zhang Z, Pereira JR, Sousa-Sa E, et al. Environmental characteristics of early childhood education
691 and care centres and young children's weight status: A systematic review. *Preventive medicine*. 2018;
692 106: 13-25.
- 693 65 Noonan K, Corman H, Schwartz-Soicher O, Reichman NE. Effects of Prenatal Care on Child Health
694 at Age 5. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*. 2013; 17: 189-99.
- 695 66 Yousefi PD, Suderman M, Langdon R, et al. DNA methylation-based predictors of health:
696 applications and statistical considerations. *Nature Reviews Genetics*. 2022; 23: 369-83.
- 697 67 Shah S, Bonder MJ, Marioni RE, et al. Improving Phenotypic Prediction by Combining Genetic
698 and Epigenetic Associations. *Am J Hum Genet*. 2015; 97: 75-85.
- 699 68 Freedman DS, Butte NF, Taveras EM, et al. BMI z - scores are a poor indicator of adiposity
700 among 2 - to 19 - year - olds with very high BMIs, NHANES 1999 - 2000 to 2013 - 2014. *Obesity*. 2017;
701 25: 739-46.
- 702 69 Durmus B, Heppe DH, Taal HR, et al. Parental smoking during pregnancy and total and
703 abdominal fat distribution in school-age children: the Generation R Study. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2014; 38:
704 966-72.
- 705 70 Camfferman R, Jansen PW, Rippe RCA, et al. The association between overweight and
706 internalizing and externalizing behavior in early childhood. *Social Science & Medicine*. 2016; 168: 35-42.
- 707 71 Lin LZ, Yang-Huang JW, Wang HJ, et al. Social mobility by parent education and childhood
708 overweight and obesity: a prospective cohort study. *Eur J Public Health*. 2021; 31: 764-70.
- 709 72 Steegers C, Dieleman G, Moskalenko V, et al. The longitudinal relationship between set-shifting
710 at 4 years of age and eating disorder related features at 9 years of age in the general pediatric
711 population. *Int J Eating Disord*. 2021.
- 712 73 Looman KIM, Santos S, Moll HA, et al. Childhood Adiposity Associated With Expanded Effector
713 Memory CD8+ and Vδ2+Vγ9+ T Cells. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2021; 106: e3923-e35.
- 714 74 Nguyen AN, van Langeveld AWB, de Vries JHM, et al. Dietary taste patterns in early childhood:
715 the Generation R Study. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2021; 113: 63-69.
- 716 75 Marciniak M, van Deutekom AW, Toemen L, et al. A three-dimensional atlas of child's cardiac
717 anatomy and the unique morphological alterations associated with obesity. *Eur Heart J Cardiovasc*
718 *Imaging*. 2022; 23: 1645-53.
- 719 76 Silva CCV, Jaddoe VWV, Sol CM, et al. Phthalate and Bisphenol Urinary Concentrations, Body Fat
720 Measures, and Cardiovascular Risk Factors in Dutch School-Age Children. *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2021;
721 29: 409-17.
- 722 77 Beunders VAA, Koopman-Verhoeff ME, Vermeulen MJ, et al. Sleep, 24-hour activity rhythms,
723 and cardiometabolic risk factors in school-age children. *J Clin Sleep Med*. 2023; 19: 1219-29.
- 724 78 Blaauwendraad SM, Stevens DR, van den Dries MA, et al. Fetal Organophosphate Pesticide
725 Exposure and Child Adiposity Measures at 10 Years of Age in the General Dutch Population. *Environ*
726 *Health Perspect*. 2023; 131: 87014.
- 727 79 Bronfenbrenner U. The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design:
728 Harvard university press 1979.
- 729 80 Withanage NN, Botfield JR, Srinivasan S, Black KI, Mazza D. Effectiveness of preconception
730 interventions in primary care: a systematic review. *Br J Gen Pract*. 2022; 72: e865-e72.

Table 1. Overview of the candidate predictors in each domain

Domains	Assessment methods	Candidate predictors	Number of variables
Sociodemographic factors	Questionnaires	Maternal and paternal education, child ethnicity	5
Preconception and prenatal parental health	Questionnaires	Maternal pre-pregnancy BMI, paternal BMI, maternal pre-pregnancy weight, maternal and paternal smoking during pregnancy, maternal and paternal cannabis use	7
Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Blood sample and questionnaires (FFQ)	Total n-6 (omega-6) polyunsaturated fatty acids, vitamin D status during pregnancy, folic acid supplement use, nausea and vomiting during pregnancy, milk intake during pregnancy	5
Maternal mental health and parenting	Questionnaires (including BSI, CFQ)	Psychopathological symptoms (GSI), depression, feeding practices (pressure to eat and restriction), the age at the first solid foods, breastfeeding duration	10
Early-life weight and weight gain	Objective measurements	Weight gain during infancy, BMI at 1.5m and 2 y, BMI gain in mid-infancy and late-infancy, BMI at estimated adiposity peak	8
Infant and childhood nutrition	Questionnaires (FFQ)	High fat-mass dietary pattern, animal and plant protein intake	2
Child behaviors	Questionnaires (including CEBQ)	Emotional undereating, emotional overeating, enjoyment of food, food responsiveness, satiety responsiveness, meal skipping (breakfast, lunch and dinner), computer gaming, television viewing, outdoor play, set-shifting	19
Biological factors	Hair sample	Cortisol concentration, cortisone concentration	2
Genetic variants	Cord blood sample	Child BMI polygenic risk score	1
Total			59

Abbreviations: BSI: Brief Symptoms Inventory; CFQ, Child Feeding Questionnaire; GSI, Global Severity Index; FFQ, Food Frequency Questionnaire; CEBQ, Child Eating Behavior Questionnaire

Table 2. Characteristics of study population (N = 5686)

	Mean (SD) or N (%)
Age of the child at BMI assessment	9.8 (0.3)
Child sex (girls)	2866 (50.4%)
Child ethnic background	
Dutch	3417 (60.1%)
Non-Dutch Western	517 (9.1%)
Non-Dutch non-western	1752 (30.8%)
Child BMI at the age of 10 years	17.6 (2.8)
Child zBMI at the age of 10 years	0.2 (1.0)
Child weight status	
Normal or underweight ^a	4663 (82.0%)
Overweight or obesity	1023 (18.0%)

Abbreviation: SD, standard deviation. Values are mean (SD) for continuous variables with a normal distribution, or valid numbers N (%) for categorical variables. Missing values of covariates were imputed with multiple imputation (20 imputations)

^a The proportion of thinness grade 2 and grade 3 in this population is 0.8%

Table 3. Associations between key predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity at age 10 years in multiple regression models (N = 5686)

Key predictors (IQR or reference category)	Time of assessment	zBMI		Overweight or obesity	
		β (95% CI)		OR (95% CI)	
<i>Sociodemographic factors</i>					
Child ethnic background (ref: Dutch)	Baseline				
Non-Dutch Western		0.13 (0.05, 0.22)		1.76 (1.27, 2.44)	
Non-Dutch Non-Western		0.12 (0.05, 0.19)		1.65 (1.26, 2.17)	
Maternal education (ref: high)	Baseline				
Middle		-		1.49 (1.17, 1.91)	
Low		-		1.68 (1.22, 2.32)	
Paternal education (ref: high)	Baseline			1.52 (1.17, 1.98)	
Middle		-		1.51 (1.11, 2.05)	
Low		-		1.49 (1.17, 1.91)	
Maternal education (ref: high)	5 years				
Middle		0.12 (0.06, 0.17)		-	
Low		0.20 (0.10, 0.29)		-	
Paternal education (ref: high)	5 years				
Middle		0.09 (0.03, 0.15)		-	
Low		0.09 (0.01, 0.17)		-	
<i>Preconception and prenatal parental health</i>					
Maternal BMI (4.4 kg/m ²)	Before pregnancy	0.17 (0.14, 0.20)		1.46 (1.31, 1.62)	
Paternal BMI (4.2 kg/m ²)	Baseline	0.17 (0.14, 0.21)		1.49 (1.30, 1.70)	
Maternal smoking (ref: no)	During pregnancy				
Until pregnancy		0.03 (-0.05, 0.11)		1.12 (0.82, 1.55)	
Continued		0.11 (0.05, 0.17)		1.26 (0.97, 1.63)	
<i>Maternal nutrition during pregnancy</i>					
Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids (3.3%)	During pregnancy	-		1.18 (1.01, 1.37)	
Vitamin D concentration, 25(OH)D (48.4 nmol/L)	During pregnancy	-0.08 (-0.12, -0.04)		0.76 (0.63, 0.91)	
Folic acid supplement use (ref: start periconceptional)	During pregnancy				
Start first 10 weeks		0.08 (0.02, 0.13)		1.26 (0.98, 1.61)	
Never		0.05 (-0.04, 0.14)		1.25 (0.91, 1.71)	
Milk intake (ref: <1 glasses)	During pregnancy				
1 – <2 glasses		0.01 (-0.05, 0.07)		0.90 (0.69, 1.17)	
2 – <3 glasses		0.01 (-0.05, 0.07)		0.82 (0.61, 1.10)	
≥3 glasses		0.05 (-0.03, 0.13)		1.11 (0.8, 1.53)	

<i>Maternal mental health and parenting</i>			
The timing of introduction of solid foods (ref: ≥ 5 months)	During infancy		
4-<5 months		-	1.17 (0.86, 1.60)
<4 months		-	1.21 (0.83, 1.76)
Breastfeeding duration (ref: ≥ 6 months)	During infancy		
4-<6 months		-	1.11 (0.78, 1.59)
2-<4 months		-	0.99 (0.72, 1.35)
<2 months		-	0.92 (0.67, 1.26)
Pressure to eat (6 unit of sum score)	4 years	-0.05 (-0.08, -0.01)	-
Restriction (9 units of sum score)	10 years	0.18 (0.13, 0.22)	1.56 (1.31, 1.85)
<i>Early-life weight and weight gain</i>			
Weight gain during infancy (1110 g)	0 to 6 months	0.07 (0.03, 0.11)	-
Weight gain during infancy (760 g)	6 to 12 months	0.07 (0.03, 0.10)	1.19 (1.05, 1.35)
Weight gain during infancy (1100 g)	12 to 24 months	0.10 (0.07, 0.14)	1.28 (1.12, 1.47)
zBMI (1.3 SD)	1.5 months	0.08 (0.04, 0.12)	1.29 (1.11, 1.50)
zBMI (1.4 SD)	2 years	0.28 (0.23, 0.33)	1.86 (1.58, 2.19)
BMI at estimated adiposity peak (1.1 kg/m ²)	-	0.17 (0.12, 0.23)	-
<i>Infant and childhood nutrition</i>			
High fat-mass dietary pattern (1.2 unit of component scores)	1 year	0.06 (0.01, 0.10)	1.14 (0.96, 1.34)
Animal and plant protein intake (15.8 g)	1 year	0.03 (-0.01, 0.06)	1.08 (0.95, 1.23)
<i>Child behaviors</i>			
Enjoyment of food (4 units of sum score)	4 years	-0.05 (-0.09, -0.01)	-
Emotional overeating (4 units of sum score)	10 years	-	1.13 (0.98, 1.31)
Food responsiveness (5 units of sum score)	10 years	0.25 (0.21, 0.28)	2.14 (1.89, 2.42)
Satiety responsiveness (8 units of sum score)	10 years	-0.18 (-0.21, -0.15)	0.64 (0.56, 0.74)
Breakfast skipping (ref: no)	6 years	0.22 (0.12, 0.32)	1.79 (1.26, 2.54)
Television viewing (ref: <2 hours/day)	6 years	0.08 (0.03, 0.13)	-
Outdoor play (ref: >1 hour/day)	6 years	-	0.89 (0.66, 1.20)
Set-shifting (10 units of sum score)	4 years	-0.06 (-0.10, -0.03)	0.84 (0.72, 0.98)
Explained variance (R^2)		49.2% (47.0%, 51.4%)	33.7% ^a

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; DSA, deletion-substitution-addition; IQR, interquartile range; OR, odds ratio; SD, standard deviation. Predictors selected in at least 10% DSA models were identified as key predictors. Since the DSA algorithm was performed separately for zBMI and weight status, a set of key predictors was identified for each outcome. These key predictors were then included simultaneously in the multiple linear

regression model for zBMI and the logistic regression model for weight status, respectively. Predictors not modeled in a given outcome were marked with a '-' in the table.

For continuous variables, β represent differences in zBMI per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, β represent differences of zBMI in comparison category vs. reference categories. For continuous variables, OR represent differences in odds of overweight or obesity per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, OR represent differences of odds of overweight or obesity in comparison category vs. reference categories. IQR and reference categories are indicated in the bracket for predictors.

^a McFadden's pseudo R^2 was calculated for explained variance in the odds of being overweight and obesity at the age of 10 years.

Figure legend

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Figure 2. Explained variance in child BMI at age 10 year

This figure illustrates the relative explained variance by 25 key predictors selected for BMI at age 10 years. Each segment of the outer level of the pie chart corresponds to predictors of zBMI listed in sequential order as presented in Table 3. The key predictors explained 49.2% of the variance in zBMI at age 10. The decomposition of R^2 shows that key predictors in preconception and prenatal parental health (8.9%), early-life weight and weight gain (20.2%), and child behavior (10.5%) domains accounted for the largest proportions of explained variance, with maternal prepregnancy BMI, paternal BMI, child BMI at age 2, BMI at adiposity peak, food responsiveness and satiety responsiveness at age 10 each constituting a substantial portion within their respective domains.

Figure 3. Explained variance in childhood overweight and obesity at age 10 years

This figure illustrates the relative explained variance by 25 key predictors selected for overweight and obesity at age 10 years. Each segment of the outer level of the pie chart corresponds to predictors of overweight and obesity listed in sequential order as presented in Table 3. The key predictors combined explained 33.7% variance in the odds of having overweight or obesity at age 10 years. The decomposition of R^2 shows that key predictors in the preconception and prenatal parental health (5.8%), early-life weight and weight gain (9.5%), and child behavior (11.1%) domains constituted the largest proportions. Within these domains, maternal prepregnancy BMI, paternal BMI, child BMI at age 2, food responsiveness and satiety responsiveness at age 10 accounted for substantial proportions.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Identifying key predictors of mid-childhood obesity in a population-based cohort study: An evidence synthesis and predictive modeling study

Yuchan Mou^{1,2}, Susana Santos^{2,3,4}, Macarena Lara¹, Ivonne P.M. Derks^{5,6,7}, Vincent W.V. Jaddoe^{1,2,3}, Romy Gaillard^{1,2,3}, Janine F. Felix^{2,3}, Eric Steegers⁸, Trudy Voortman^{1,9}, Marinus H. van IJzendoorn^{10,11}, Pauline W. Jansen^{5,6}

Affiliations

1. Department of Epidemiology, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, The Netherlands
2. The Generation R Study Group, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, The Netherlands
3. Department of Pediatrics, Erasmus MC, University, Medical Center Rotterdam, The Netherlands
4. EPIUnit ITR, Instituto de Saúde Pública da Universidade do Porto, Universidade do Porto, Rua das Taipas, n° 135, 4050-600 Porto, Portugal
5. Department of Psychology, Education and Child Studies, Erasmus University Rotterdam, The Netherlands
6. Department of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry / Psychology, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, The Netherlands
7. Research Department of Behavioural Science and Health, University College London, United Kingdom
8. Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, Netherlands
9. Meta-Research Innovation Center at Stanford (METRICS), Stanford University, Stanford, CA, USA
10. Department of Psychiatry, Monash University, Melbourne, Australia
11. Research Department of Clinical, Education and Health Psychology, UCL, University of London, UK

Corresponding author: Pauline W. Jansen, Dr. Molewaterplein 40, PO Box 2040, 3000 CA, Rotterdam, the Netherlands,

p.w.jansen@erasmusmc.nl

Table of Content

Supplementary Methods 1. Search strategy

Supplementary Methods 2. Assessment of predictors

Supplementary Methods 3. Multiple imputation

Table S1. Statistics conversion methods

Table S2. Effect sizes computation and conversion to Fisher's z methods

Table S3. Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation

Table S4. Overview of included papers

Table S5. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in sociodemographics factors domain

Table S6. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in preconception and prenatal parental health domain

Table S7. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in maternal nutrition during pregnancy domain

Table S8. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in genetics domain

Table S9. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in maternal mental health and parenting domain

Table S10. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in early-life weight and weight gain domain

Table S11. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in infant and childhood nutrition domain

Table S12. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in child behaviors domain

Table S13. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in biological factors domain

Table S14. Descriptive statistics for all predictors included in multiple regression models (n = 5686)

Table S15. Associations between key predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity in multiple regression models including child BMI polygenic risk score (N = 3584)

Table S16. Associations between key predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity in multiple regression models stratified by child sex (N = 5686)

Table S17. Associations between key predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity in multiple regression models stratified by child ethnic background (N = 5686)

Table S18. Associations between predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity at age 10 years in parsimonious multiple regression models (N = 5686)

Reference list of publications included in the evidence synthesis

Figure S1. Forest plots for predictors of child BMI with pooled effect sizes above the threshold ($|d| \geq 0.1$)

Figure S2. Cross-validation plots based on DSA-selected models for (A) BMI and (B) overweight and obesity in children aged 10 years

Supplementary Methods 1. Search strategy

Pubmed

(Drooger JC[Author] AND (Moll, Ha[Full Author Name] OR Moll HA[Author] OR Moll HA[Investigator])) OR (Rours GI[Author] AND (pregnant[Title] OR (pregnan*[Title] AND cohort[Title]))) OR (Gabriele C[Author] AND (Moll, Ha[Full Author Name] OR Moll HA[Author] OR Moll HA[Investigator])) OR (Verburg BO[Author] AND Jaddoe VW[Author]) OR (“family characteristics”[MeSH Terms] OR (“family”[All Fields] AND “characteristics”[All Fields]) OR “family characteristics”[All Fields] OR “generation”[All Fields]) AND Jaddoe V[Author]) OR (Verkaik NJ[Author] AND Jaddoe VW[Author]) OR (van den Berg MP[Author] AND Jaddoe VW[Author]) OR (Witteman JC[Author] AND Jaddoe VW[Author] AND Hypotheses[All fields] OR Jaddoe VW[Author] AND Mook-Kanamori DO[Author])

Embase

embase is not capital sensitive ('Drooger J':au AND 'Moll H':au) OR ('Rours G':au AND (pregnant:ti OR (pregnan AND cohort):ti)) OR ('Gabriele C':au AND 'Moll H':au) OR ('Verburg B':au AND 'Jaddoe V':au) OR ('Jaddoe V':au AND generation) OR ('Verkaik N':au AND 'Jaddoe V':au) OR ('van den Berg M':au AND 'Jaddoe V':au) OR ('Witteman J':au AND 'Jaddoe V':au AND 'Hypotheses' OR 'Jaddoe V':au AND 'Mook-Kanamori D':au)

OV Medline

(Drooger J.au AND Moll H.au) OR (Rours G.au AND (pregnant OR (pregnan AND cohort)) .ti) OR (Gabriele C.au AND Moll H.au) OR (Verburg B.au AND Jaddoe V.au) OR (“generation r”.ti,ab OR Jaddoe V.au) AND Rotterdam.in) OR (Verkaik N.au AND Jaddoe V.au) OR (van den Berg M.au AND Jaddoe V.au) OR (Witteman J.au AND Jaddoe V.au AND Hypotheses OR Jaddoe V.au AND Mook-Kanamori D*.au)

Web of Science ((AU=Drooger J* AND AU=Moll H) OR (AU=Rours G AND (TI=“pregnant” OR TI= (“pregnan” AND “cohort”)))) OR (AU=Gabriele C AND AU=Moll H) OR (AU=Verburg B AND AU=Jaddoe V) OR ((TS= (“generation R”) OR AU=jaddoe v) AND (AD=rotterdam)) OR (AU=Verkaik N AND AU=Jaddoe V) OR (AU=van den Berg M AND AU=Jaddoe V) OR (AU=Witteman J AND AU=Jaddoe V* AND TS=“Hypotheses” OR AU=Jaddoe V* AND AU=Mook-Kanamori D*))

Supplementary methods 2

Sociodemographic factors

Child ethnic background was defined by the country of birth of the parents, as obtained by questionnaires¹ and grouped children into Dutch, Non-Dutch Western and non-Dutch Non-Western ethnic origin. Information about the parents' education was obtained by questionnaire during pregnancy and when the children were 6 years old. We categorized the educational level into three groups: (1) low (no education, primary school, lower vocational training, intermediate general school, or ≤ 3 years general secondary school); (2) middle (>3 years general secondary school, intermediate vocational training); and (3) high (higher vocational training, university degree).

Preconception and prenatal parental health

Maternal pre-pregnancy weight was obtained by self-report questionnaires. Maternal and paternal weight and height were measured without shoes and heavy clothing at enrolment² and BMI was calculated as weight/height^2 (kg/m^2). Information about maternal smoking during pregnancy was assessed by questionnaires in the first, second and third trimester of pregnancy³. We categorized mothers' smoking status into three groups: (1) never smoked during pregnancy; (2) smoked until their pregnancy was known; (3) continued to smoke during pregnancy. Paternal smoking was reported by mothers on whether father smoked cigarettes, cigars or shag in early pregnancy (yes, no or do not know).

Maternal and paternal information on cannabis use was collected by a mother-reported questionnaire in early pregnancy. We grouped maternal cannabis use into four categories: (1) never used cannabis; (2) used cannabis before pregnancy; (3) used cannabis until their pregnancy was known; (4) continued cannabis use during pregnancy. Paternal cannabis use was dichotomized (never vs ever used).

Maternal nutrition during pregnancy

Non-fasting venous blood sample were collected in the second trimester of pregnancy at a median gestational age of 20.5 weeks (95% range 16.5 – 24.9). Total and individual n-6 Polysaturated fatty acids (PUFA) concentrations were expressed as the proportion of total fatty acids that were present in the chromatogram (weight percentage), including linoleic acid (LA; 18:2n-6), gamma-linolenic acid (GLA; 18:3n-6), eicosadienoic acid (EDA; 20:2n-6), dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid (DGLA; 20:3n-6), arachidonic acid (AA; 20:4n-6), and docosatetraenoic acid (DTA; 22:4n-6)⁴. Plasma 25-hydroxyvitamin D₂ (25(OH)D₂) and 25(OH)D₃ were quantified using isotope dilution liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry and summed to Total 25(OH)D⁵. Periconceptional folic acid supplement use was assessed in the first trimester by questionnaire. We categorized mothers into not using supplementation, started in the first trimester (before 10 weeks), and started preconceptionally⁶. Information about maternal vomiting and nausea was obtained by questionnaires at enrollment in early pregnancy and was categorized into: (1) no daily vomiting versus (2) daily vomiting during early pregnancy.

Maternal milk intake during early pregnancy (median: 13.5 weeks of gestation, 95% range 10.8, 21.1) was assessed by a semi-quantitative food-frequency questionnaire (FFQ) consisting of 293 food items. We summed the consumption of milk and milk drinks (e.g., chocolate milk or other flavored, sweetened milk drinks) to obtain frequency measures of milk consumption. According to the

Dutch household measures, 1 glass of milk contains 150 milliliter milk on average⁷. We categorized maternal milk intake into 4 groups: <1, 1-<2, 2-<3, and ≥ 3 glasses per day.

Genetic variants

A child BMI polygenic risk score (PGS) was constructed using identified genetic loci associated with childhood BMI from a large consortium study, in which the Generation R Study was involved⁸. Briefly, 25 loci that achieved genome-wide significance were combined into a polygenic risk score by summing up the weighted number of risk alleles that are associated with an increase in BMI standardized deviation score (SDS). The weights accounted for genetic variant-specific effect sizes and were derived from the meta-analysis in the consortium study. The PGS ranges from 0 to 50. In this study population, genetic data was available for 3584 children whose height and weight were measured at the age of 10 years.

Maternal mental health and parenting

Information on maternal psychopathology symptoms was collected by the validated, self-reported Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI)⁹, assessing symptoms of anxiety, depression, hostility, interpersonal sensitivity, obsessive-compulsive disorder, psychoticism, paranoia, phobia, and somatization. Items are reported on 5-point Likert scale. At 20 weeks of gestation, the full 53-item BSI was administered, from which we calculated a Global Severity Index (GSI) by summing all items, indicating the overall psychopathology symptoms.

Postpartum depression symptom was calculated by summing the items of the depression scale measured at 20 weeks, 2 months and 6 months.

Information on the age at introduction of the first solid foods and duration of exclusive breastfeeding was obtained from postnatal questionnaires at 2, 6, and 12 months after birth. Feeding practices were assessed with the Child Feeding Questionnaire (CFQ) when children were 4 and 10 years of age, including pressure to eat (attempting to improve the quantity or quality of children's food intakes;) and restriction (regulating the type and amount of food eaten by children) as subscales¹⁰. The items were answered on a 5-point Likert Scale and summed per subscale.

Early-life weight and weight gain

Infant weight and length were measured in community health centers at ages 6, 12, and 24 months. Weight was measured with a mechanical personal scale. Length was measured in a supine position to the nearest millimeter with a neonatometer. BMI was calculated as kg/m^2 . Age- and sex- adjusted SDS of weight, length and BMI were obtained using Dutch reference growth charts (Growth Analyzer 3.5)¹¹. Weight gain and BMI-SDS gain were quantified as the difference between assessment time points. BMI at estimated adiposity peak in infancy was obtained using a cubic mixed effect model fitted on $\log(\text{BMI})$ from 14 days to 1.5 years, using sex as a covariate. BMI was derived for each child at the point where the curve reached its maximum¹².

Infant and childhood nutrition

Dietary intake was assessed at the age of 1 year with a semi-quantitative FFQ consisting of 211 food items. Food frequencies were converted into energy and macronutrient intake based on the standardized portion sizes and the Dutch Food Composition Table 2006¹³. Protein intake was divided into protein from animal food sources (e.g., dairy) and from plant-based food sources (e.g., grains).

The *a posteriori* dietary patterns used in the study were extracted by reduced rank regression¹⁴, which explained the maximal variance in fat mass index and fat-free mass index. The dietary pattern derived from fat-mass and fat-free mass index was characterized by high intake of refined grains, meat, potatoes, fish, soups and sauces, and sugar-containing beverages.

Child behavior

Child eating behaviors were assessed using the Children's Eating Behavior Questionnaire (CEBQ) at ages 4 and 10 years, including the subscales emotional undereating, emotional overeating, enjoyment of food, food responsiveness, and satiety responsiveness¹⁵. Parents rated their children's eating behavior tendencies on a 5-point Likert Scale. Children's consumption of breakfast, lunch, and dinner were assessed by single-item questions reported on by parents when children were 4 and 6 years old¹⁶. At 4 years, the Brief Rating Inventory of Executive Function-Preschool Version¹⁷ was administered to measure functions including set-shifting ability (i.e. cognitive flexibility, which is the ability to move back and forth between tasks, operations or mental sets) with three response options (0 = never to 2 = very often/aways). Sedentary and physical activity behaviors were assessed by parent-reported questionnaire when the child was 6 years old. In this study, sedentary behaviors included television viewing (including video/DVD) and computer/video game use; physical activity included outdoor play. For all variables, the frequency and duration were asked for weekdays and weekend days separately. We

categorized average television viewing into ≥ 2 h/day and < 2 h/day, and computer game use into ≥ 1 h/day and < 1 h/day. Outdoor play was dichotomized into < 1 hour/day versus ≥ 1 hour/day¹⁸.

Other biological factors

Hair glucocorticoid was measured using hair samples of around 100-200 strands that were cut from the posterior vertex close to the scalp. Cortisol and cortisone were measured simultaneously with a liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) assay. Briefly, the proximal 3 cm of hair samples were weighed using an electrical scale and minced. Hair samples were then washed in LC-grade isopropanol for 2 min at room temperature, and left to dry for at least 2 days. Deuterium-labeled cortisol and cortisone were added before extraction. Extraction was performed using LC-grade methanol (MeOH), for 18 h at 25 °C in the presence of deuterated steroids. Subsequently, the extract was cleaned using solid phase extraction and steroids were quantified on a Xevo TQS LC-MS/MS (Waters Corporation, Milford, MA, USA)¹⁹.

Supplementary Methods 3

Multiple imputation

Missing values of candidate predictors, except child BMI PRS, were imputed using multiple imputation under the assumption of missingness at random. Potential variables used to impute missing values of another variable were restricted to those that had: 1) an absolute correlation greater than 0.1 with the variable or with the binary missing variable indicating if the variable is missing; and 2) a proportion of missing observations less than 50%. These restrictions ensured that the number of variables used to impute was within the range of 5-25, as including no more than 25 variables is recommended in missing imputation model specification²⁰. Continuous variables with a skewed distribution were entered in the imputation process with original scales, as Box-Cox power transformations to achieve normality were not sufficient. We forced child ethnicity, maternal education, and family income into the imputation model as these variables are related to the probability of missingness of variables. Twenty imputed data sets were generated and used in subsequent analyses.

After imputation, numeric and graphic diagnostics proposed for cohort studies were conducted to ensure the imputation was done properly²¹. Continuous variables were flagged if they had 1) an absolute difference between means of the observed and imputed values greater than 2 standard deviations; or 2) a ratio of variances of the observed and imputed values that is less than 0.5 or greater than 2. Categorical variables were flagged if the chi-squared test between observed and imputed values was significant. In the current study, no variables were flagged.

References

- 1 Gishti O, Kruithof CJ, Felix JF, et al. Ethnic disparities in general and abdominal adiposity at school age: a multiethnic population-based cohort study in the Netherlands. *Ann Nutr Metab.* 2014; 64: 208-17.
- 2 Jharap VV, Santos S, Steegers EAP, Jaddoe VWV, Gaillard R. Associations of maternal obesity and excessive weight gain during pregnancy with subcutaneous fat mass in infancy. *Early Hum Dev.* 2017; 108: 23-28.
- 3 Durmus B, Heppe DH, Taal HR, et al. Parental smoking during pregnancy and total and abdominal fat distribution in school-age children: the Generation R Study. *Int J Obes (Lond).* 2014; 38: 966-72.
- 4 Vidakovic AJ, Gishti O, Voortman T, et al. Maternal plasma PUFA concentrations during pregnancy and childhood adiposity: the Generation R Study. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2016; 103: 1017-25.
- 5 Miliku K, Felix JF, Voortman T, et al. Associations of maternal and fetal vitamin D status with childhood body composition and cardiovascular risk factors. *Matern Child Nutr.* 2018; 15: e12672.
- 6 Monasso GS, Santos S, Geurtsen ML, et al. Associations of Early Pregnancy and Neonatal Circulating Folate, Vitamin B-12, and Homocysteine Concentrations with Cardiometabolic Risk Factors in Children at 10 y of Age. *J Nutr.* 2021; 151: 1628-36.
- 7 Donders-Engels MR, van der Heijden L, Maten HK. Gewichten en Codenummers [Weights, measures and code numbers]. Wageningen (Netherlands): Vakgroep Humane Voeding, Landbouwniversiteit Wageningen en TNO Voeding Zeist 2003.
- 8 Vogelesang S, Bradfield JP, Ahluwalia TS, et al. Novel loci for childhood body mass index and shared heritability with adult cardiometabolic traits. *PLOS Genetics.* 2020; 16: e1008718.
- 9 Derogatis LR, Melisaratos N. The Brief Symptom Inventory: an introductory report. *Psychological Medicine.* 1983; 13: 595-605.
- 10 Birch LL, Fisher JO, Grimm-Thomas K, et al. Confirmatory factor analysis of the Child Feeding Questionnaire: a measure of parental attitudes, beliefs and practices about child feeding and obesity proneness. *Appetite.* 2001; 36: 201-10.
- 11 Fredriks AM, van Buuren S, Wit JM, Verloove-Vanhorick SP. Body index measurements in 1996-7 compared with 1980. *Arch Dis Child.* 2000; 82: 107-12.
- 12 Mook-Kanamori DO, Durmuş B, Sovio U, et al. Fetal and infant growth and the risk of obesity during early childhood: the Generation R Study. *Eur J Endocrinol.* 2011; 165: 623-30.
- 13 Dutch food composition database 2006 (NEVO 2006). The Hague, The Netherlands: Netherlands Nutrition Center.
- 14 Voortman T, Leermakers ET, Franco OH, et al. A priori and a posteriori dietary patterns at the age of 1 year and body composition at the age of 6 years: the Generation R Study. *Eur J Epidemiol.* 2016; 31: 775-83.
- 15 Wardle J, Guthrie CA, Sanderson S, Rapoport L. Development of the Children's Eating Behaviour Questionnaire. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry.* 2001; 42: 963-70.
- 16 Mou Y, Jansen PW, Raat H, Nguyen AN, Voortman T. Associations of family feeding and mealtime practices with children's overall diet quality: Results from a prospective population-based cohort. *Appetite.* 2021; 160: 105083.

- 17 Gioia GA, Isquith PK, Retzlaff PD, Espy KA. Confirmatory factor analysis of the Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function (BRIEF) in a clinical sample. *Child Neuropsychol.* 2002; 8: 249-57.
- 18 Wijtzes AI, Bouthoorn SH, Jansen W, et al. Sedentary behaviors, physical activity behaviors, and body fat in 6-year-old children: the generation R study. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act.* 2014; 11: 96.
- 19 Noppe G, van den Akker EL, de Rijke YB, et al. Long-term glucocorticoid concentrations as a risk factor for childhood obesity and adverse body-fat distribution. *Int J Obes (Lond).* 2016; 40: 1503-09.
- 20 van Buuren S, Groothuis-Oudshoorn K. mice: Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations in R. *Journal of Statistical Software.* 2011; 45: 1 - 67.
- 21 Stuart EA, Azur M, Frangakis C, Leaf P. Multiple Imputation With Large Data Sets: A Case Study of the Children's Mental Health Initiative. *American Journal of Epidemiology.* 2009; 169: 1133-39.

Supplementary Tables

In this supplementary tables file, we presented the methods for converting different original statistics (median, mean, beta/B) into statistics (mean(sd) and β) used in the effect sizes computation in **Table S1**. **Table S2** presents the methods and formula of effect sizes computation and conversion into Fisher's z statistics which used in the meta-analysis. **Table S3** shows percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for imputation. **Table S4** presents the overview of characteristics of included papers. **Table S5-S13** show the pooled effect sizes of predictors within each domain. We used Cohen's $d = 0.1$ as the cut-off value. Values of effect sizes which were colored as **red** denote that effect size values larger than the cut-off, and values of effect sizes which were colored as **blue** denote that effect size values smaller than the cut-off. **Table S14-18** report the results from sensitivity analyses.

Table S1. Statistics conversion methods

Predictors Type	Original effect size statistics	After conversion	Method
categorical	Mean, 95% <i>CI</i>	Mean, <i>SD</i>	$SD = \frac{(Upperlimit-Lower)}{2*1.96*\sqrt{\frac{(n+1)}{n}}}$
categorical	Median, range or <i>IQR</i>	Mean, <i>SD</i>	Used <i>method 3</i> 'the first quartile, median, the third quartile, sample size' proposed by <i>X. Wan et al, 2014</i>
categorical	Median, 90% or 95% range	Mean, <i>SD</i>	90% or 95% range proxy to range. Then used <i>method 1</i> 'minimum, median, maximum, sample size' proposed by <i>X. Wan et al, 2014</i>
Continuous	B	β	$\beta = B \frac{sd_x}{sd_y}$

¹ *CI*: confidence interval; *SD*: standard deviation; *IQR*: interquartile range

Table S2. Effect sizes computation and conversion to Fisher's z methods

Predictors Type	Information needed ⁴	Methods ^{1, 3, 4}
Categorical	$\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, sd_1, sd_2, n_1, n_2$	<p>(1) We calculated SMD: $ES_{smd} = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{sd_{pooled}}, v_{smd} = \frac{n_1 + n_2}{n_1 * n_2} + \frac{ES_{smd}^2}{2 * (n_1 + n_2)}$, where $sd_{pooled} = \sqrt{\frac{sd_1^2 * (n_1 - 1) + sd_2^2 * (n_2 - 1)}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}$.</p> <p>(2) SMD was converted to r. $r = \frac{ES_{smd}}{\sqrt{ES_{smd} + \frac{1}{p * (1-p)}}}$, $v_r = \frac{v_{smd}}{v_{smd} + \frac{1}{p * (1-p)}}$.</p> <p>(3), r was converted to Fisher's z: $z_r = 0.5 * \log(\frac{1+r}{1-r})$, $v_z = \frac{1}{n-3}$. Functions in R 'esc' package²: <i>esc_mean_sd()</i> and <i>convert_d2r()</i>.</p>
Categorical	$B/\beta, sd_y, n_1, n_2$	<p>For B: (1) We calculated SMD: $ES_{smd} = \frac{B}{sd_{pooled}}, v_{smd} = \frac{n_1 + n_2}{n_1 * n_2} + \frac{ES_{smd}^2}{2 * (n_1 + n_2)}$, where $sd_{pooled} = \sqrt{\frac{sd_y^2 * (n_1 + n_2 - 1) - B^2 * \frac{(n_1 * n_2)}{n_1 + n_2}}{n_1 + n_2 - 2}}$.</p> <p>(2) SMD was converted to r: same as above. (3) r was converted to Fisher's z using the same formula as above. For β: $B = \beta * \frac{sd_y}{sd_x}$. Then the same formula as B was used. Functions in R 'esc' package: <i>esc_B()</i> for B, <i>esc_beta()</i> for beta.</p>

Predictors Type	Information needed ⁴	Methods ^{1, 3, 4}
Categorical	B/β , exact p value, n_1, n_2	<p>(1) We calculated the point-biserial correlation coefficient r_{pb}:</p> $t = (p \text{ value}, k),$ $r_{pb} = \sqrt{\frac{t^2}{n_1+n_2-2+t^2}},$ <p>where degree of freedom $k = n_1 + n_2 - 2$.</p> <p>(2) the SMD can be computed by:</p> $ES_{smd} = \frac{r_{pb}}{\sqrt{p(1-p)(1-r_{pb}^2)}},$ $v_{smd} = \frac{n_1+n_2}{n_1*n_2} + \frac{ES_{smd}^2}{2*(n_1+n_2)},$ <p>where $p = \frac{n_1}{n_1+n_2}$.</p> <p>(3) SMD converted to r:</p> $r = \frac{ES_{smd}}{\sqrt{ES_{smd}^2 + \frac{1}{p*(1-p)}}}, v_r = \frac{v_{smd}}{v_{smd} + \frac{1}{p*(1-p)}}.$ <p>(4) r converted to z use the same formula as above.</p> <p>Functions in R 'esc' package: <code>esc_rpb()</code> and <code>convert_d2r()</code>.</p>
Continuous	r, n_{total}	r was converted to Fisher's z using the same formula as above.
Continuous	β, n_{total}	We extracted β from unadjusted models (or considered as unadjusted effect sizes if there were no unadjusted effect sizes presented in the study), therefore β equals to r . r was converted to Fisher's z using the same formula as above.

¹ Lipsey MW, Wilson DB. Practical meta-analysis: SAGE publications, Inc 2001.

² Lüdtke D, Lüdtke MD, Calculator' from David BW. Package 'esc'. R Package Version 05. 2019; 1: 2019.

³ \bar{x}_1, sd_1, n_1 is mean, standard deviation, number of comparison group, \bar{x}_2, sd_2, n_2 is mean, standard deviation, number of reference group. sd_y is standard deviation of BMI.

⁴ sd : standard deviation; smd : standardized mean difference.

Table S3. Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation

Incomplete variables	Percentages of missing values (%)	Method used for imputation
Child sex	0.02	Logistic regression
Maternal age	0.02	Predictive mean matching
Child ethnic background	2.34	Polytomous logistic regression
Parity	3.18	Polytomous logistic regression
Maternal education - baseline	8.02	Polytomous logistic regression
Maternal smoking during pregnancy	12.59	Polytomous logistic regression
Maternal cannabis use	12.94	Logistic regression
Maternal education - 5 years	14.60	Polytomous logistic regression
Breakfast skipping - 6 years	14.93	Logistic regression
Satiety responsiveness - 10 years	16.16	Predictive mean matching
Enjoyment of food - 10 years	16.30	Predictive mean matching
Food responsiveness - 10 years	16.37	Predictive mean matching
Lunch skipping - 6 years	16.58	Logistic regression
Restriction - 10 years	16.74	Predictive mean matching
Dinner skipping - 6 years	17.69	Logistic regression
Emotional overeating - 10 years	18.75	Predictive mean matching
Household income - 5 years	18.92	Logistic regression
Paternal smoking during pregnancy	19.70	Logistic regression
Paternal cannabis use	20.93	Logistic regression
Television viewing	21.35	Logistic regression
Maternal vomiting and nausea	21.61	Logistic regression
Paternal education - 5 years	21.81	Polytomous logistic regression
Household income - baseline	22.35	Logistic regression
25(OH)D concentration	23.72	Predictive mean matching
Computer game use	23.92	Logistic regression
Maternal weight before pregnancy	24.74	Predictive mean matching
Maternal BMI before pregnancy	24.85	Predictive mean matching
Weight gain during infancy - 0 to 6 months	24.90	Predictive mean matching
Psychopathology symptoms (GSI)	25.34	Predictive mean matching
Postpartum depression - 20 weeks	25.36	Predictive mean matching
BMI at estimated adiposity peak	25.36	Predictive mean matching

Table S3. Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Percentages of missing values (%)	Method used for imputation
Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids	25.75	Predictive mean matching
Maternal milk intake during pregnancy	28.39	Polytomous logistic regression
Outdoor play	28.46	Logistic regression
Paternal BMI - baseline	29.26	Predictive mean matching
Pressure to eat - 2 years	29.32	Predictive mean matching
Folic acid supplement use	30.51	Polytomous logistic regression
Breakfast skipping - 4 years	32.11	Logistic regression
Food responsiveness - 4 years	32.25	Predictive mean matching
Satiety responsiveness - 4 years	32.31	Predictive mean matching
Lunch skipping - 4 years	32.43	Logistic regression
Pressure to eat - 4 years	32.52	Predictive mean matching
Emotional undereating - 4 years	32.64	Predictive mean matching
Set-shifting	32.64	Predictive mean matching
Restriction - 4 years	32.73	Predictive mean matching
Enjoyment of food - 4 years	32.73	Predictive mean matching
Dinner skipping - 4 years	32.87	Logistic regression
Emotional overeating - 4 years	33.05	Predictive mean matching
Weight gain during infancy - 6 to 12 months	34.79	Predictive mean matching
zBMI - 2 years	34.93	Predictive mean matching
Paternal education - baseline	37.34	Polytomous logistic regression
Postpartum depression - 2 months	38.11	Predictive mean matching
Breastfeeding duration	42.21	Proportional odds model
BMI gain during infancy - 6 to 12 months	42.46	Predictive mean matching
Weight gain during infancy - 12 to 24 months	43.95	Predictive mean matching
Postpartum depression - 6 months	44.44	Predictive mean matching
zBMI - 1.5 months	44.44	Predictive mean matching
BMI gain during infancy - 12 to 24 months	45.25	Predictive mean matching
Timing of introduction of solid foods	45.87	Polytomous logistic regression
Animal and plant protein intake	51.79	Predictive mean matching
Hair cortisol concentration	59.22	Predictive mean matching

Table S3. Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Percentages of missing values (%)	Method used for imputation
Hair cortisone concentration	59.90	Predictive mean matching
Timing of introduction of solid foods	66.44	Predictive mean matching

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Child ethnic background	Maternal education-baseline, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Parity, Maternal age
Maternal education-baseline	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Enjoyment of food-10 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
Maternal education-5 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Paternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Enjoyment of food-10 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Parity, Maternal age
Paternal education-baseline	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Maternal cannabis use, Paternal cannabis use, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
Paternal education-5 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Paternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal cannabis use, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Maternal BMI before pregnancy	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, 25(OH)D concentration, zBMI-1.5 months, zBMI-2 years, BMI at estimated adiposity peak, Food responsiveness-10 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Paternal BMI before pregnancy	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal weight before pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, zBMI-1.5 months, zBMI-2 years, BMI at estimated adiposity peak, Food responsiveness-10 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity
Maternal weight before pregnancy	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Weight gain during infancy-6 to 12 months, Weight gain during infancy-12 to 24 months, zBMI-2 years, Food responsiveness-10 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years
Maternal smoking during pregnancy	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
Paternal smoking during pregnancy	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
Maternal cannabis use	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, 25(OH)D concentration, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years
Paternal cannabis use	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Postpartum depression-2 months, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
25(OH)D concentration	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Breakfast skipping-6 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
Folic acid supplement use	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Emotional overeating-4 years, Breakfast skipping-4 years, Lunch skipping-4 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Parity, Maternal age

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Maternal vomiting and nausea	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
Maternal milk intake during pregnancy	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years
Psychopathology symptoms (GSI)	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Pressure to eat-4 years, Restriction-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-4 years, Breakfast skipping-4 years, Lunch skipping-4 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Computer game use, Set-shifting, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
Postpartum depression-20 weeks	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Set-shifting, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
Postpartum depression-2 months	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Restriction-10 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
Postpartum depression-6 months	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Computer game use, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Pressure to eat-2 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Pressure to eat-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Enjoyment of food-10 years, Food responsiveness-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Restriction-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Restriction-10 years, Emotional overeating-10 years, Food responsiveness-10 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Restriction-10 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI-2 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Timing of introduction of solid foods	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Breastfeeding duration	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Computer game use, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child sex, Maternal age
Weight gain during infancy-6 to 12 months	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal weight before pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
Weight gain during infancy-12 to 24 months	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal weight before pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Enjoyment of food-10 years, Food responsiveness-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
zBMI-1.5 months	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Paternal BMI before pregnancy, Folic acid supplement use, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Computer game use, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity
zBMI-2 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Paternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal weight before pregnancy, Folic acid supplement use, Restriction-10 years, Enjoyment of food-10 years, Food responsiveness-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
BMI gain-6 to 12 months	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
BMI gain-12 to 24 months	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
BMI at estimated adiposity peak	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Paternal BMI before pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Food responsiveness-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, Computer game use, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child sex, Parity, Maternal age
High fat-mass dietary pattern	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Postpartum depression-2 months, Pressure to eat-4 years, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
Animal and plant protein intake	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-baseline, Paternal education-5 years, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Emotional undereating-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Emotional overeating-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Emotional overeating-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Restriction-10 years, Emotional overeating-10 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Enjoyment of food-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Enjoyment of food-10 years, Food responsiveness-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Food responsiveness-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Restriction-10 years, Emotional overeating-10 years, Enjoyment of food-10 years, Food responsiveness-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Satiety responsiveness-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Enjoyment of food-10 years, Food responsiveness-10 years, Satiety responsiveness-10 years, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Emotional overeating-10 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Parity, Maternal age
Enjoyment of food-10 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI-2 years, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Food responsiveness-10 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Paternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal weight before pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI-2 years, BMI at estimated adiposity peak, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Satiety responsiveness-10 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI-2 years, BMI at estimated adiposity peak, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Breakfast skipping-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Lunch skipping-6 years, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Lunch skipping-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Lunch skipping-6 years, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Dinner skipping-4 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Lunch skipping-6 years, Dinner skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Breakfast skipping-6 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Lunch skipping-6 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Incomplete variables	Variables used for imputing each incomplete variable
Dinner skipping-6 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Computer game use	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child sex, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Television viewing	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Outdoor play	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Set-shifting	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child sex, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Hair cortisol	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years
Hair cortisone	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Hair cortisol, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child sex

Table S3 Percentages of missing values in each predictor and variables used for multiple imputation (continued)

Household income-5 years	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal BMI before pregnancy, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal cannabis use, Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, 25(OH)D concentration, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, zBMI at age 10, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10, Maternal age
Household income-baseline	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, Paternal education-5 years, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Weight gain during infancy-0 to 6 months, Breakfast skipping-6 years, Computer game use, Television viewing, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Parity, Maternal age
Child sex	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Computer game use, Hair cortisone, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years
Parity	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal education-5 years, BMI at estimated adiposity peak, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Maternal age
Maternal age	Child ethnic background, Maternal education-baseline, Maternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal smoking during pregnancy, Paternal cannabis use, Folic acid supplement use, Maternal vomiting and nausea, Psychopathology symptoms (GSI), Postpartum depression-20 weeks, zBMI at age 10, Household income-5 years, Child age at BMI assessment at age 10

Table S4. Overview of included papers¹

Authors	Years	Domains	Predictors	Age at predictors assessment	Age at BMI assessment	Sample size
O. Gishti, C. J. Kruithof et al.	2014	Sociodemographic factors	Ethnicity	At enrollment	6 years	5244
O. Gishti, R. Gaillard, J. F. Felix et al.	2015	Sociodemographic factors	Ethnicity	At enrollment	6 years	5054
R. Gaillard, A. A. Rurangirwa et al.	2014	Sociodemographic factors	Parity	First trimester	6 years	6295
L. van Rossem et al.	2010	Sociodemographic factors	Maternal education	At enrollment	3 years	2954
S. H. Bouthoorn, A. I. Wijtzes et al.	2014	Sociodemographic factors	Maternal education	At enrollment	6 years	3010
L. Lin et al.	2021	Sociodemographic factors	Maternal education	At enrollment	10 years	4030
L. Ay el al.	2008	Sociodemographic factors	Sex	At enrollment	2 years	1012
E. T. Leermakers, J. F. Felix, N. S. Erler et al.	2015	Sociodemographic factors	Sex	At enrollment	6 years	2045
S. Vogelezang et al.	2016	Sociodemographic factors	Sex	At enrollment	6 years	393
T. Marinkovic et al.	2017	Sociodemographic factors	Sex	At enrollment	6 years	4649
A. N. Nguyen et al.	2020	Sociodemographic factors	Sex	At enrollment	10 years	3991
A. Elhakeem et al.	2022	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Assisted reproductive technology use	At enrollment	10 years	3796
M. N. Kooijman et al.	2016	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Umbilical artery pulsatility index	Third trimester	6 years	1195
R. Gaillard et al.	2013	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Umbilical artery pulsatility index	Third trimester	6 years	4722
J. L. Vinther et al.	2023	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Gestational age	At enrollment	10 years	3870
M. Lecorguille el al.	2023	Preconception and prenatal parental health	High parental smoking, and low maternal diet quality	First, second, and third trimesters	10 years	4944
B. Durmus, L. Ay et al.	2011	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal smoking	First, second, and third trimesters	2 years	671
B. Durmus, C. J. Kruithof et al.	2011	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal smoking	First, second, and third trimesters	4 years	5342
K. N. Cajachagua-Torres et al.	2022	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal tabacco use	First, second, and third trimesters	10 years	4252
B. Durmus, D. H. Heppe, H. R. Taal et al.	2014	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Paternal smoking	First, second, and third trimesters	6 years	3832

Table S4. Overview of included papers¹ (continued)

Authors	Years	Domains	Predictors	Age at predictors assessment	Age at BMI assessment	Sample size
M. Welten et al.	2015	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Haemoglobin	Second trimester	6 years	4995
R. J. Wahab et al.	2021	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal dietary glyceimic index	First trimester	10 years	2483
R. J. Wahab et al.	2020	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal glucose concentrations	First trimester	10 years	3726
G. A. Godoy et al.	2014	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Thyroid stimulating hormone levels	First trimester	6 years	3985
R. Gaillard et al.	2015	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Gestational weight gain	First trimester	6 years	4062
V. V. Jharap et al.	2017	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal BMI	Preconception	2 years	659
R. C. Richmond et al.	2017	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal BMI	Preconception	6 years	2337
R. Gaillard, E. A. Steegers et al.	2014	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal BMI	Preconception	6 years	4871
L. Benschop et al.	2018	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal BMI	Preconception	10 years	4479
S. Santos et al.	2019	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Maternal BMI	Preconception	10 years	2354
B. Durmus, L. R. Arends et al.	2013	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Paternal BMI	Preconception	4 years	3055
D. V. Gootjes et al.	2021	Preconception and prenatal parental health	Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy	At enrollment	6 years	5312
A. Jelena Vidakovic, S. Santos et al.	2016	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Total n-3 PUFA	Second trimester	2 years	904
A. J. Vidakovic, O. Gishti et al.	2016	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Total n-3 PUFA	Second trimester	6 years	4830
T. Voortman et al.	2018	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	n-6 PUFA pattern	Second trimester	6 years	4890
E. Voerman et al.	2016	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Cafeine intake	First, second, and third trimesters	6 years	5562

Table S4. Overview of included papers¹ (continued)

Authors	Years	Domains	Predictors	Age at predictors assessment	Age at BMI assessment	Sample size
E. Voerman et al.	2020	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Caffeine intake	First, second, and third trimesters	10 years	4754
E. Voerman et al.	2021	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Milk intake	First trimester	10 years	2461
V. Jen et al.	2017	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Total sugar-containing beverage intake	First trimester	6 years	3312
M. van den Broek et al.	2015	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Vegetable, fish, and oil dietary pattern	First trimester	6 years	2689
H. G. Quezada-Pinedo et al.	2023	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Ferritin	First trimester	10 years	3711
S. Poeran-Bahadoer et al.	2020	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Maternal vomiting	First trimester	6 years	4760
M. J. Tielemans et al.	2017	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Total protein intake	First trimester	6 years	2694
G. S. Monasso et al.	2021	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Folate	First trimester	10 years	3701
K. Miliku et al.	2018	Maternal nutrition during pregnancy	Maternal 25 (OH) D	Second trimester	6 years	4898
C. Monnereau et al.	2016	Genetics	Adult BMI genetic risk score	At birth	6 years	3975
S. Vogelesang et al.	2015	Genetics	Adult BMI genetic risk score	At birth	6 years	4144
C. Monnereau et al.	2017	Genetics	Child BMI genetic risk score	At birth	4 years	2413
C. Monnereau et al.	2018	Genetics	Child BMI genetic risk score	At birth	10 years	1993
F. P. Velders et al.	2012	Genetics	Child FTO	At birth	4 years	1718
J. A. Maas et al.	2010	Genetics	INS VNTR	At birth	2 years	738
S. H. Bouthoorn, F. J. van Lenthe et al.	2014	Genetics	PROP taster status	6 year(s)	6 years	5894
B. Durmus, D. H. Heppe, O. Gisht et al.	2014	Maternal mental health and parenting	Breastfeeding	2, 6 and 12 months	6 years	5063

Table S4. Overview of included papers¹ (continued)

Authors	Years	Domains	Predictors	Age at predictors assessment	Age at BMI assessment	Sample size
S. Voegelezang et al.	2018	Maternal mental health and parenting	Breastfeeding	2, 6 and 12 months	10 years	4444
K. A. Ertel et al.	2012	Maternal mental health and parenting	Depression	Second trimester	3 years	6782
M. Guxens et al.	2013	Maternal mental health and parenting	Depression	Second trimester	4 years	5273
F. O. L. Vehmeijer et al.	2019	Maternal mental health and parenting	Distress	Second trimester	10 years	4147
P. W. Jansen et al.	2014	Maternal mental health and parenting	Pressure to eat	2 year(s)	4 years	2361
I. P. Derks, H. Tiemeier et al.	2017	Maternal mental health and parenting	Restriction	10 year(s)	10 years	4689
P. W. Jansen et al.	2020	Maternal mental health and parenting	Using food as reward	4 year(s)	10 years	3642
S. Santos et al.	2016	Early-life weight and weight gain	BMI-1.5mo	1.5 months	6 years	742
B. Patro Golab et al.	2019	Early-life weight and weight gain	Total subcutaneous fat mass	2 months	10 years	593
V. W. Jaddoe et al.	2014	Early-life weight and weight gain	Fetal growth restriction	First trimester	6 years	1184
O. Gishti, R. Gaillard, R. Manniesing et al.	2014	Early-life weight and weight gain	Length gain fetal	Second trimester	6 years	5447
C. J. Kruithof et al.	2016	Early-life weight and weight gain	Peak weight velocity	36 months	6 years	5118
S. Voegelezang et al.	2019	Early-life weight and weight gain	Weight status for gestational age	At birth	10 years	3205
H. R. Taal et al.	2013	Early-life weight and weight gain	Weight strata for gestational age combined with catch up/down growth	0-2 year(s)	4 years	3531
A. N. Nguyen et al.	2020	Infant and childhood nutrition	Total carbohydrate intake (10g/d)	1 year(s)	10 years	3573
W. Stroobant et al.	2017	Infant and childhood nutrition	Total fat intake (5E%)	1 year(s)	6 years	2967
T. Voortman, E. T. Leermakers et al.	2016	Infant and childhood nutrition	Diet quality score	1 year(s)	6 years	2026
E. T. Leermakers, J. F. Felix, V. W. Jaddoe et al.	2015	Infant and childhood nutrition	Sugar containing beverage intake	1 year(s)	6 years	2371

Table S4. Overview of included papers¹ (continued)

Authors	Years	Domains	Predictors	Age at predictors assessment	Age at BMI assessment	Sample size
T. Voortman, K. V. Braun et al.	2016	Infant and childhood nutrition	Total protein intake	1 year(s)	6 years	2911
K. V. Braun et al.	2016	Infant and childhood nutrition	Total protein intake	1 year(s)	10 years	3564
V. Jen et al.	2019	Infant and childhood nutrition	Total protein intake (5E%)	1 year(s)	10 years	3573
E. T. Leermakers, J. C. Kiefte-de Jong	2015	Infant and childhood nutrition	Lutein intake	1 year(s)	6 years	2440
K. V. Braun et al.	2015	Infant and childhood nutrition	Vitamin B6	1 year(s)	6 years	2922
A. I. Wijtzes et al.	2016	Child behaviors	Breakfast skipping	4 year(s)	6 years	5913
I. P. M. Derks et al.	2018	Child behaviors	Emotional overeating	10 year(s)	10 years	3331
P. W. Jansen et al.	2019	Child behaviors	Emotional overeating	4 year(s)	10 years	3960
P. W. Jansen et al.	2012	Child behaviors	Emotional undereating	4 year(s)	4 years	3157
L. M. de Barse et al.	2015	Child behaviors	Fussy eating profile	4 year(s)	6 years	4191
A. B. Bowling et al.	2018	Child behaviors	ADHD	9 year(s)	10 years	3901
I. P. M. Derks et al.	2019	Child behaviors	Aggressive behavior	6 year(s)	10 years	3974
R. Camfferman et al.	2016	Child behaviors	Externalizing	2 year(s)	6 years	4961
J. D. Mackenbach et al.	2012	Child behaviors	Internalizing	3 year(s)	4 years	3137
C. Steegers et al.	2021	Child behaviors	Set-shifting	4 year(s)	10 years	3829
I. P. M. Derks, D. Kocevskaja et al.	2017	Child behaviors	Sleep duration	2 months	6 years	3909
H. A. Harris et al.	2022	Child behaviors	ADHD traits	6 year(s)	14 years	3438
A. I. Wijtzes et al.	2013	Child behaviors	Sedentary behavior	2 year(s)	2 years	347
A. I. Wijtzes et al.	2014	Child behaviors	TV viewing	6 year(s)	6 years	5913
M. A. Jansen et al.	2015	Biological factors	Anti-tissue Transglutaminase concentrations	6 year(s)	6 years	4306
G. Noppe et al.	2016	Biological factors	Cortisol	6 year(s)	6 years	2953
O. L. Florianne	2021	Biological factors	Cortisol	6 year(s)	10 years	2042

¹ Gray shading is used to visually distinguish predictors from different domains.

Table S5. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in sociodemographics factors domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	CI.low	CI.hi
Maternal education	High	2	10	0.57	0.53	0.61
Ethnicity	Dutch	12	6	0.39	0.26	0.52
Paternal education	High	2	10	0.37	0.25	0.48
Maternal education	High	3	6	0.03	-0.01	0.06
Sex	Boys	3	6	0.03	-0.02	0.07
Sex	Boys	1	10	0.01	-0.02	0.04
Parity	Parity=0	4	6	-0.07	-0.12	-0.02
Maternal education	High	3	3	-0.04	-0.07	-0.01
Sex	Boys	1	2	-0.04	-0.10	0.02

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S6. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in preconception and prenatal parental health domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Maternal pre-pregnancy weight	NA	1	10	0.31	0.25	0.37
High parental BMI and low smoking	NA	1	10	0.28	0.25	0.30
Maternal BMI	NA	2	10	0.28	0.11	0.45
Maternal BMI	NA	3	6	0.25	0.19	0.31
High maternal BMI and low smoking	NA	1	10	0.24	0.22	0.27
Paternal BMI	NA	1	6	0.22	0.20	0.25
Maternal smoking	No	2	6	0.1	-0.11	0.30
Paternal BMI	NA	1	2	0.1	0.02	0.18
Maternal BMI	NA	1	2	0.19	0.12	0.27
Maternal Pre-pregnant weight	NA	1	2	0.19	0.12	0.26
Paternal BMI	NA	1	4	0.18	0.15	0.22
Maternal cannabis use	No	3	10	0.17	0.07	0.28
Maternal BMI	NA	1	4	0.17	0.14	0.21
High parental smoking, high paternal BMI, and dhigh maternal diet quality	NA	1	10	0.16	0.13	0.19
Paternal cannabis use	No	1	10	0.13	0.10	0.16
Paternal smoking	No	1	6	0.13	0.10	0.16
Paternal tobacco use	No	1	10	0.13	0.10	0.16
Umbilical artery resistance index	NA	1	6	0	-0.03	0.03
Gestational age	NA	1	10	0	-0.03	0.03
Maternal tobacco use	No	2	10	0.09	-0.05	0.23
Maternal insulin concentrations	NA	1	10	0.08	0.05	0.11
Gestational weight gain	NA	1	4	0.08	0.04	0.12
Gestational weight gain	NA	1	10	0.08	0.03	0.13
High parental smoking, and low maternal diet quality	NA	1	10	0.05	0.02	0.08
Maternal smoking	No	4	2	0.05	-0.01	0.12
Maternal smoking	No	4	4	0.05	0.00	0.10

Table S6. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in preconception and prenatal parental health domain¹ (continued)

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Maternal dietary glycemic index	NA	1	10	0.05	0.01	0.09
Maternal weight during pregnancy	NA	3	10	0.05	-0.05	0.14
High maternal smoking and dietary inflammatory potential and low DASH	NA	1	10	0.04	0.01	0.07
Maternal glucose concentrations	NA	1	10	0.04	0.01	0.07
Middel cerebral artery pulsatility index	NA	1	6	0.03	-0.03	0.09
Gestational weight gain	NA	6	6	0.02	0.00	0.04
Assisted reproductive technology use	Natural conception	1	10	0.01	-0.02	0.04
Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy	No HDP	1	6	0.01	-0.02	0.03
Free thyroxine levels	NA	1	6	-0.07	-0.10	-0.04
Umbilical/Middle cerebral artery ratio	NA	1	6	-0.06	-0.12	0.00
Maternal weight during pregnancy	NA	3	2	-0.04	-0.08	0.01
Umbilical artery pulsatility index	NA	2	6	-0.01	-0.03	0.02
Haemoglobin	NA	1	6	-0.01	-0.03	0.02
Thyroid stimulating hormone levels	NA	1	6	-0.01	-0.04	0.02
Gestational weight gain	NA	1	2	-0.01	-0.09	0.07

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S7. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in maternal nutrition during pregnancy domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Maternal vomiting	Without daily vomiting	1	6	0.26	0.23	0.28
Vegetable, fish, and oil dietary pattern	Qartile 1	3	6	0.1	0.06	0.14
Milk intake	0-0.9 glass	5	10	0.15	0.10	0.20
Total n-6 PUFA	NA	1	6	0.11	0.08	0.14
DTA (22:4 n-6)	NA	1	2	-0.1	-0.17	-0.04
AA (20:4 n-6)	NA	1	2	-0.11	-0.18	-0.05
Folic acid supplement use	No	2	10	-0.11	-0.23	0.01
Maternal 25 (OH) D	NA	1	6	-0.11	-0.13	-0.08
Homocysteine	NA	2	10	0	-0.03	0.02
EDA (20:2 n-6)	NA	1	6	0	-0.03	0.03
Lemonade from concentrate intake	NA	1	6	0	-0.03	0.03
Soda intake	NA	1	6	0	-0.04	0.03
Total protein intake	Quantile 1	3	6	0	-0.04	0.03
AA (20:4 n-6)	NA	1	6	0.09	0.06	0.12
DTA (22:4 n-6)	NA	1	6	0.08	0.05	0.11
n-6 PUFA pattern	NA	1	6	0.07	0.04	0.10
Transferrin	NA	1	10	0.07	0.04	0.10
DGLA (20:3 n-6)	NA	1	6	0.06	0.03	0.09
Caffeine intake	< 2 units	3	10	0.05	-0.15	0.25
Animal protein intake	Quantile 1	3	6	0.05	0.01	0.08
DHA (22:6 n-3)	NA	1	2	0.04	-0.03	0.11
Nuts, soy, and high-fiber cereals dietary pattern	Qartile 1	3	6	0.04	0.01	0.08
EDA (20:2 n-6)	NA	1	2	0.03	-0.04	0.10
GLA (18:3 n-6)	NA	1	6	0.03	0.00	0.06
LA (18:2 n-6)	NA	1	2	0.03	-0.04	0.10
LA (18:2 n-6)	NA	1	6	0.03	0.00	0.06
Total n-6 PUFA	NA	1	2	0.03	-0.04	0.10
Cafeine intake	<2 units	6	6	0.03	-0.03	0.10

Table S7. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in maternal nutrition during pregnancy domain¹ (continued)

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Active B12	NA	2	10	0.03	0.00	0.05
EPA (20:5 n-3)	NA	1	2	0.02	-0.05	0.09
Total n-3 PUFA	NA	1	2	0.02	-0.05	0.09
Margarine, snacks, and dietary pattern	Qartile 1	3	6	0.02	-0.02	0.06
Total B12	NA	2	10	0.02	-0.01	0.04
DGLA (20:3 n-6)	NA	1	2	0.01	-0.06	0.08
Fruit juice intake	NA	1	6	0.01	-0.03	0.04
Total sugar-containing beverage intake	NA	1	6	0.01	-0.02	0.04
Total n-3 PUFA	NA	1	6	-0.09	-0.12	-0.06
ALA (18:3 n-3)	NA	1	6	-0.08	-0.11	-0.05
DHA (22:6 n-3)	NA	1	6	-0.08	-0.11	-0.05
DPA (22:5 n-3)	NA	1	2	-0.08	-0.15	-0.01
EPA (20:5 n-3)	NA	1	6	-0.08	-0.11	-0.05
Trasferrin saturation	NA	1	10	-0.08	-0.11	-0.05
GLA (18:3 n-6)	NA	1	2	-0.07	-0.14	0.00
n-3 PUFA pattern	NA	1	6	-0.06	-0.09	-0.03
DPA (22:5 n-3)	NA	1	6	-0.05	-0.08	-0.02
Cord blood 25 (OH) D	NA	1	6	-0.05	-0.08	-0.02
Ferritin	NA	1	10	-0.04	-0.07	-0.01
Vegetable protein intake	Quantile 1	3	6	-0.04	-0.08	-0.01
ALA (18:3 n-3)	NA	1	2	-0.03	-0.10	0.04
Folate	NA	2	10	-0.03	-0.06	0.00
MUFA and SFA pattern	NA	1	6	-0.02	-0.05	0.01

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S8. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in genetics domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Hypothalamic expression and regulation genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.1	0.07	0.13
rs7185735 (SAT)	NA	1	10	0.12	0.08	0.16
Adult WHR genetic risk score	NA	2	6	0	-0.03	0.02
Child BMI genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.09	0.06	0.12
rs2123685 (SAT female)	NA	1	10	0.09	0.05	0.13
Adult BMI genetic risk score	NA	2	6	0.08	0.01	0.14
Membrane proteins genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.08	0.05	0.11
rs10182181 (ADCY3/POMC)	NA	1	4	0.08	0.04	0.12
Monogenic obesity/energy homeostasis genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.07	0.04	0.10
WNTSignaling genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.06	0.03	0.09
GR-gene (GR-9β)	NA	1	6	0.06	0.03	0.09
Muscle biology genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.05	0.02	0.08
Glucose homeostasis/diabetes genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.05	0.02	0.08
Immune system genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.05	0.02	0.08
Retinoic acid receptors genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.05	0.02	0.08
CyclicAMP genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.05	0.02	0.08
Child BMI genetic risk score	NA	1	4	0.04	0.00	0.08
Cell cycle genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.04	0.01	0.07
Limb development genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.04	0.01	0.07
Mitochondrial genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.04	0.01	0.07
Tumorigenesis genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.04	0.01	0.07
GR-gene (BclI)	NA	1	6	0.04	0.01	0.07
rs11030104 (BDNF)	NA	1	4	0.04	0.00	0.08
Adult BMI genetic risk score	NA	1	10	0.03	-0.01	0.07
Child BMI genetic risk score	NA	1	10	0.03	-0.01	0.07

Table S8. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in genetics domain¹ (continued)

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Apoptosis genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.03	0.00	0.06
Child FTO	AT	2	4	0.03	-0.02	0.08
JAK genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.03	0.00	0.06
MAPK1/extracellular signal-regulated kinases genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.03	0.00	0.06
Maternal BMI alleles score	NA	1	6	0.02	-0.02	0.06
Hormone metabolism/regulation genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.02	-0.01	0.05
PROP taster status	Non-taster	1	6	0.02	-0.01	0.04
Lipid biosynthesis and metabolism genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.02	-0.01	0.05
Neuronal developmental processes genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.02	-0.01	0.05
Neuronal expression genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.02	-0.01	0.05
rs2842895 (VAT and VATadjBMI)	NA	1	10	0.02	-0.02	0.06
Bone development genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.02	-0.01	0.05
Adult BMI genetic risk score	NA	1	4	0.01	-0.03	0.05
Eye-related genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.01	-0.02	0.04
Purine/pyrimidine cycle genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.01	-0.02	0.04
INS VNTR	I/I	2	2	0.01	-0.07	0.10
Neurotransmission genetic risk score	NA	1	6	0.01	-0.02	0.04
rs10733682 (LMX1B)	NA	1	4	0.01	-0.03	0.05
rs4256980 (TUB)	NA	1	4	-0.07	-0.11	-0.03
rs10060123 (VAT and VATadjBMI female)	NA	1	10	-0.06	-0.10	-0.02
GR-gene (ER22/23EK)	NA	1	6	-0.05	-0.08	-0.02
rs10938397 (GNPDA2)	NA	1	4	-0.05	-0.09	-0.01

Table S8. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in genetics domain¹ (continued)

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
rs6567160 (MC4R)	NA	1	4	-0.05	-0.09	-0.01
IGF1	Homozygous	2	2	-0.04	-0.12	0.04
GR-gene (N363S)	NA	1	6	-0.04	-0.07	-0.01
Adult pericardial fat genetic risk score	NA	1	10	-0.03	-0.07	0.01
Notch signaling genetic risk score	NA	1	6	-0.03	-0.06	0.00
rs1558902 (FTO)	NA	1	4	-0.03	-0.07	0.01
rs3736485 (SCG3)	NA	1	4	-0.02	-0.06	0.02
rs3888190 (SH2B1)	NA	1	4	-0.02	-0.06	0.02
rs7164727 (BBS4)	NA	1	4	-0.02	-0.06	0.02
Adult WHR genetic risk score	NA	1	10	-0.01	-0.05	0.03
Adult fatty liver genetic risk score	NA	1	10	-0.01	-0.05	0.03
VAT/SAT ratio genetic risk score	NA	1	10	-0.01	-0.05	0.03
Nuclear trafficking genetic risk score	NA	1	6	-0.01	-0.04	0.02
Endocytosis/exocytosis genetic risk score	NA	1	6	-0.01	-0.04	0.02
Ubiquitin pathways genetic risk score	NA	1	6	-0.01	-0.04	0.02

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S9. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in maternal mental health and parenting domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Distress	No stress	1	10	0.42	0.39	0.46
Timing of first solid foods	>= 5 months	2	10	0.22	0.08	0.37
Timing of first solid foods	>= 5 months	4	6	0.16	0.10	0.21
Breastfeeding	Ever breastfed	1	10	0.14	0.11	0.17
Depression	No	3	3	0.13	0.08	0.19
Restriction	NA	2	10	0.12	-0.09	0.32
Pressure to eat	NA	1	6	-0.13	-0.17	-0.09
Pressure to eat	NA	2	4	-0.12	-0.27	0.03
Family stress	NA	1	4	0	-0.03	0.03
Using food as reward	NA	1	10	0	-0.03	0.03
Use of food to soothe	Never	2	10	0.09	-0.09	0.27
Restriction	NA	1	4	0.09	0.06	0.13
Restriction	NA	1	6	0.08	0.04	0.12
Breastfeeding	Ever breastfed	2	6	0.07	-0.01	0.15
Hostility	NA	1	4	0.06	0.03	0.09
Breastfeeding exclusivity	Exclusive until 4 months of age	1	10	0.05	0.02	0.08
Duration of breastfeeding	>= 6 months	3	10	0.05	-0.02	0.11
Breastfeeding exclusivity	Exclusive until 4 months of age	2	6	0.04	0.00	0.07
Depression	NA	1	4	0.04	0.01	0.06
Anxiety	NA	1	4	0.03	0.01	0.06
Duration of breastfeeding	>= 6 months	6	6	0.02	-0.02	0.06
Monitoring	NA	1	6	-0.07	-0.10	-0.04
Monitoring	NA	1	4	-0.01	-0.04	0.02

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S10. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in early-life weight and weight gain domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
BMI-2y	NA	1	6	0.58	0.50	0.65
BMI at adiposity peak	NA	1	6	0.52	0.50	0.55
Peak weight velocity	NA	1	6	0.41	0.38	0.44
Weight strata for gestational age combined with catch up/down growth	Appropriate GA, no catch up/catch down	6	4	0.3	0.20	0.39
BMI-1.5mo	NA	1	6	0.22	0.15	0.30
Weight gain infancy	NA	3	6	0.22	0.14	0.29
Total subcutaneous fat mass	NA	2	6	0.21	-0.04	0.45
BMI gain-infancy	NA	2	6	0.16	0.11	0.21
Central-to-total fat mass ratio	NA	3	6	0.12	0.04	0.20
Fetal growth restriction	NA	1	6	-0.79	-0.85	-0.74
Total subcutaneous fat mass	NA	3	10	0.09	0.00	0.19
Weight gain fetal	NA	2	6	0.07	0.04	0.09
Central-to-total fat mass ratio	NA	3	10	0.06	-0.01	0.13
Fetal and infant growth	Fetal normal - infant normal	8	6	0.05	-0.29	0.38
Abdominal circumference	NA	1	6	0.04	0.01	0.07
Length gain fetal	NA	2	6	0.04	-0.02	0.11
Age at adiposity peak	NA	1	6	0.03	0.00	0.06
Length gain infancy	NA	3	6	0.03	0.00	0.07
Weight status for gestational age	Appropriate GA	2	10	0.03	-0.09	0.16

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S11. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in infant and childhood nutrition domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
High FMI dietary pattern	NA	1	6	0.14	0.10	0.18
Plant protein intake	NA	1	10	0.14	0.11	0.17
Animal protein intake	NA	1	10	0.13	0.10	0.16
Total fat intake	NA	1	6	0	-0.04	0.04
High FFMI dietary pattern	NA	1	6	0	-0.04	0.04
Total monosaccharide and disaccharide intake (10g/d)	NA	1	10	0	-0.03	0.03
Total protein intake	NA	1	6	0.08	0.04	0.11
Total protein intake	NA	1	10	0.08	0.05	0.11
Animal protein intake	NA	1	10	0.06	0.03	0.10
Total protein intake	NA	1	10	0.06	0.03	0.10
Diet quality score	NA	1	6	0.05	0.01	0.09
Animal protein intake	NA	1	6	0.05	0.01	0.09
Health-conscious dietary patterns	NA	1	6	0.04	0.00	0.08
Western dietary pattern	NA	1	6	0.04	0.00	0.08
Folate	Tertile 1 (<80.9)	2	6	0.04	0.00	0.07
Sugar containing beverage intake	Low intake (<3 servings/w)	4	6	0.03	-0.02	0.08
Vegetable protein intake	NA	1	6	0.03	0.00	0.07
SFAs	NA	1	6	0.02	-0.01	0.06
Diet quality score	NA	2	10	0.01	-0.06	0.09
Vegetable protein intake	NA	1	10	0.01	-0.02	0.04
Lutein intake	NA	1	6	0.01	-0.03	0.05
Methionine	Tertile 1 (<681.5)	2	6	0.01	-0.02	0.05
Vitamin B12	Tertile 1 (<2.2)	2	6	0.01	-0.02	0.05
Vitamin B6	Tertile 1 (<1.1)	2	6	0.01	-0.02	0.05
Folic acid	Tertile 1 (<304.3)	2	6	-0.04	-0.07	0.00
Folate equivalent	Tertile 1 (<167.8)	2	6	-0.03	-0.06	0.01
PUFAs	NA	1	6	-0.02	-0.05	0.02
Total carbohydrate intake (10g/d)	NA	1	10	-0.01	-0.04	0.02
MUFAs	NA	1	6	-0.01	-0.04	0.03
Total polysaccharide intake (10g/d)	NA	1	10	-0.01	-0.04	0.02

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S12. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in child behaviors domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Breakfast skipping	No	2	6	0.32	0.20	0.44
Food responsiveness	NA	4	10	0.26	0.13	0.39
Food responsiveness	NA	2	4	0.22	0.20	0.25
Emotional overeating	NA	4	10	0.1	0.04	0.16
Lunch skipping	No	2	6	0.19	0.07	0.32
TV viewing	< 2 hrs/day	1	6	0.19	0.17	0.22
Enjoyment of food	NA	2	4	0.16	0.14	0.19
Enjoyment of food	NA	2	10	0.15	0.03	0.27
Dinner skipping	No	2	6	0.13	-0.01	0.27
Computer game	< 1 hr/day	1	6	0.12	0.09	0.15
Outdoor play	>= 1 hr/day	1	6	0.12	0.09	0.15
Set-shifting	NA	2	10	-0.35	-0.91	0.21
Satiety responsiveness	NA	2	4	-0.24	-0.27	-0.22
Satiety responsiveness	NA	2	10	-0.22	-0.35	-0.09
Emotional undereating	NA	2	4	-0.1	-0.13	-0.08
ADHD traits	<80th percentile	1	14	0.05	0.02	0.09
Externalizing	NA	3	6	0.04	0.02	0.06
Sports participation	Yes	1	6	0.04	0.01	0.07
Emotional overeating	NA	2	4	0.03	0.01	0.05
ADHD	No ADHD diagnosis	2	10	0.03	-0.06	0.11
Aggressive behavior	NA	2	10	0.02	-0.01	0.04
Internalizing	NA	3	6	0.02	-0.03	0.07
Sedentary behavior	NA	1	2	0.02	-0.09	0.13
Desire to drink	NA	2	4	0.01	-0.01	0.03
Active transport	>= 5 days/week	1	6	-0.09	-0.12	-0.06
Fussiness	NA	2	4	-0.08	-0.10	-0.05
Fussy eating profile	Non-fussy eater	1	6	-0.08	-0.11	-0.05
Sleep duration	NA	4	6	-0.05	-0.07	-0.04
Internalizing	NA	2	4	-0.04	-0.06	-0.01
Autistic traits	<80th percentile	1	14	-0.04	-0.07	0.00
Externalizing	NA	2	4	-0.03	-0.05	-0.01
Moderate-to-vigorous physical activity	NA	1	2	-0.03	-0.14	0.08
Movement counts/minute	NA	1	2	-0.03	-0.14	0.08

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S13. Pooled effect sizes of predictors in biological factors domain¹

Predictors	Reference	Number of effect sizes	BMI time point	Cohen's d	ci.low	ci.hi
Cortisol	NA	1	6	0.6	0.57	0.64
Cortisol	0.14-0.73 pg/mg	4	10	0.27	0.14	0.40
Cortisone	NA	1	6	0.23	0.20	0.27
Anti-tissue Transglutaminase concentrations	Negative anti-tTG (<7 U/mL)	2	6	0.04	-0.01	0.08

¹ In the Cohen's d column, red highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| \geq 0.1$, and blue highlights represent summary effect sizes with $|d| < 0.1$.

Table S14. Descriptive statistics for all predictors included in multiple regression models (n = 5686)

Predictors	Time of assessment	Median [IQR] or %
<i>Sociodemographic factors</i>		
Child ethnic background	Baseline	
Dutch		60.2
Non-Dutch Western		9.1
Non-Dutch Non-Western		30.7
Maternal education	Baseline	
Low		20.3
Middle		30.7
High		49.0
Paternal education	Baseline	
Low		25.7
Middle		27.2
High		47.1
Maternal education	5 years	
Low		12.7
Middle		31.2
High		56.1
Paternal education	5 years	
Low		18.0
Middle		27.9
High		54.0
<i>Preconception and prenatal parental health</i>		
Maternal BMI, kg/m ²	Before pregnancy	22.7 [20.8, 25.2]
Paternal BMI, kg/m ²	Baseline	25.0 [23.0, 27.2]
Maternal weight	Before pregnancy	64.0 [58.0, 72.0]
Maternal smoking	Baseline	
No		76.3
Until pregnancy		8.7
Continued		15.0

<i>Maternal nutrition during pregnancy</i>		
Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids, %	During pregnancy	36.5 [34.9, 38.2]
Vitamin D concentration, 25(OH)D, nmol/L	During pregnancy	53.0 [30.4, 79.0]
Folic acid use	Baseline	
No		23.4
Start first trimester		31.9
Start periconceptional		44.7
Milk intake	During pregnancy	
<1 glasses		34.5
1 – <2 glasses		26.3
2 – <3 glasses		23.5
≥3 glasses		15.7
<i>Maternal mental health and parenting</i>		
Pressure to eat	4 years	13.0 [10.0, 16.0]
Restriction	10 years	15.0 [10.0, 19.0]
The timing of the introduction of solid foods	During infancy	
<4 months		21.8
4-<5 months		56.9
≥5 months		21.3
Breastfeeding duration	During infancy	
<2 months		29.5
2-<4 months		22.1
4-<6 months		12.9
≥6 months		35.5
<i>Early-life weight and weight gain</i>		

Weight gain during infancy, grams	0 to 6 months	4385.0 [3850.0, 4960.0]
Weight gain during infancy, grams	6 to 12 months	1730.0 [1370.0, 2130.0]
Weight gain during infancy, grams	12 to 24 months	3190.0 [2670.0, 3770.0]
zBMI, SD	1.5 months	0.5 [-0.2, 1.1]
zBMI, SD	2 years	0.2 [-0.4, 0.9]
BMI at estimated adiposity peak, kg/m ²	-	17.6 [17.0, 18.1]
<i>Infant and childhood nutrition</i>		
High fat-mass dietary pattern, units of component score	1 year	0.0 [-0.5, 0.7]
Animal and plant protein intake, grams	1 year	40.4 [32.8, 48.4]
<i>Child behaviors</i>		
Enjoyment of food, units of sum score	4 years	14.0 [12.0, 16.0]
Emotional overeating, units of sum score	10 years	4.0 [4.0, 8.0]
Food responsiveness, units of sum score	10 years	8.0 [6.0, 11.0]
Satiety responsiveness, units of sum score	10 years	23.0 [19.0, 27.0]
Breakfast skipping	6 years	
Yes		6.3
No		93.7
Television viewing	6 years	
<2 hours/day		33.3
≥2 hours/day		66.7
Outdoor play	6 years	
<1 hours/day		13.9

≥1 hours/day		86.1
Set-shifting	4 years	46.0 [42.0, 54.0]
<i>Genetic variants</i>		
BMI polygenic risk score (based on 25 SNPs)	6 years	25.0 [23.3, 26.7]

Table S15. Associations between key predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity in multiple regression models including child BMI polygenic risk score (N = 3584)

Predictors (IQR or reference category)	Time of assessment	zBMI β (95% CI)	Overweight or obesity OR (95% CI)
<i>Sociodemographic factors</i>			
Child ethnic background (ref: Dutch)	Baseline		
Non-Dutch Western		0.12 (0.01, 0.22)	1.75 (1.14, 2.68)
Non-Dutch Non-Western		0.05 (-0.06, 0.16)	1.04 (0.68, 1.58)
Maternal education (ref: high)	Baseline		
Middle		-	1.61 (1.17, 2.22)
Low		-	1.77 (1.19, 2.62)
Paternal education (ref: high)	Baseline		
Middle		-	1.45 (1.05, 2.02)
Low		-	1.26 (0.85, 1.85)
Maternal education (ref: high)	5 years		
Middle		0.12 (0.05, 0.19)	-
Low		0.19 (0.08, 0.3)	-
Paternal education (ref: high)	5 years		
Middle		0.09 (0.01, 0.16)	-
Low		0.08 (-0.02, 0.18)	-
<i>Preconception and prenatal parental health</i>			
Maternal BMI (4.4 kg/m ²)	Before pregnancy	0.18 (0.14, 0.21)	1.53 (1.34, 1.75)
Paternal BMI (4.2 kg/m ²)	Baseline	0.17 (0.14, 0.21)	1.51 (1.27, 1.79)
Maternal smoking (ref: no)	Baseline		
Until pregnancy		0.02 (-0.09, 0.12)	0.97 (0.63, 1.49)
Continued		0.12 (0.04, 0.2)	1.31 (0.95, 1.8)
<i>Maternal nutrition during pregnancy</i>			
Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids (3.3%)	During pregnancy	-	0.99 (0.82, 1.19)
Vitamin D status, 25(OH)D (48.4 nmol/L)	During pregnancy	-0.05 (-0.1, 0)	0.88 (0.7, 1.11)
Folic acid supplement use (ref: start periconceptional)	During pregnancy		
Start first 10 weeks		0.06 (0, 0.13)	1.26 (0.94, 1.7)
Never		0.04 (-0.06, 0.14)	1.3 (0.89, 1.89)

Milk intake (ref: <1 glasses)	During pregnancy		
1 – <2 glasses		-0.01 (-0.09, 0.06)	0.85 (0.6, 1.19)
2 – <3 glasses		0.01 (-0.07, 0.09)	0.79 (0.54, 1.15)
≥3 glasses		0.06 (-0.03, 0.15)	1.13 (0.75, 1.69)
<i>Maternal mental health and parenting</i>			
The timing of the introduction of solid foods (ref: ≥5 months)	During infancy		
4-<5 months		-	1.21 (0.83, 1.77)
<4 months		-	1.19 (0.73, 1.92)
Breastfeeding duration (ref: ≥6 months)	During infancy		
4-<6 months		-	1.22 (0.77, 1.95)
2-<4 months		-	1.02 (0.7, 1.49)
<2 months		-	0.91 (0.63, 1.31)
Pressure to eat (6 unit of sum score)	4 years	-0.03 (-0.08, 0.01)	-
Restriction (9 units of sum score)	10 years	0.13 (0.08, 0.18)	1.48 (1.18, 1.86)
<i>Early-life weight and weight gain</i>			
Weight gain during infancy (1110 g)	0 to 6 months	0.05 (0, 0.1)	-
Weight gain during infancy (760 g)	6 to 12 months	0.07 (0.03, 0.11)	1.18 (1.01, 1.37)
Weight gain during infancy (1100 g)	12 to 24 months	0.09 (0.05, 0.13)	1.28 (1.06, 1.53)
zBMI (1.3 SD)	1.5 months	0.09 (0.04, 0.15)	1.34 (1.08, 1.67)
zBMI (1.4 SD)	2 years	0.28 (0.22, 0.34)	1.99 (1.62, 2.44)
BMI at estimated adiposity peak (1.1 kg/m ²)	-	0.17 (0.11, 0.23)	-
<i>Infant and childhood nutrition</i>			
High fat-mass dietary pattern (1.2 unit of component scores)	1 year	0.05 (0, 0.1)	1.12 (0.94, 1.34)
Animal and plant protein intake (15.8 g)	1 year	0.03 (-0.02, 0.07)	1.11 (0.95, 1.31)
<i>Child behaviors</i>			
Enjoyment of food (4 units of sum score)	4 years	-0.03 (-0.08, 0.01)	-
Emotional overeating (4 units of sum score)	10 years	-	1.1 (0.91, 1.34)
Food responsiveness (5 units of sum score)	10 years	0.24 (0.2, 0.28)	2.25 (1.9, 2.68)
Satiety responsiveness (8 units of sum score)	10 years	-0.17 (-0.21, -0.13)	0.73 (0.61, 0.88)
Breakfast skipping (ref: no)	6 years	0.22 (0.1, 0.35)	1.81 (1.13, 2.9)
Television viewing (ref: <2 hours/day)	6 years	0.06 (0, 0.12)	-
Outdoor play (ref: >1 hour/day)	6 years	-	0.87 (0.59, 1.28)
Set-shifting (10 units of sum score)	4 years	-0.05 (-0.09, -0.01)	0.88 (0.73, 1.07)

<i>Genetic variants</i>			
Child BMI polygenic risk scores (3.4 additional average risk allele)		0.14 (0.1, 0.18)	1.45 (1.23, 1.7)
Explained variance (R^2)		48.7% (46.1%, 51.2%)	35.2% ^a

Predictors selected in at least 10% DSA models were identified as key predictors. Since the DSA algorithm was performed separately for zBMI and weight status, a set of key predictors was identified for each outcome. These key predictors were then included simultaneously in the multiple linear regression model for zBMI and the logistic regression model for weight status, respectively. Predictors not modeled in a given outcome were marked with a ‘-’ in the table.

For continuous variables, β represent differences in zBMI per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, β represent differences of zBMI in comparison category vs. reference categories. For continuous variables, OR represent differences in odds of overweight and obesity per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, OR represent differences of odds of overweight and obesity in comparison category vs. reference categories. IQR and reference categories are indicated in the bracket for predictors. Models include all key predictors selected by the DSA algorithm and child BMI polygenic risk scores.

^a McFadden’s pseudo R^2 was calculated for explained variance in the odds of being overweight and obesity at the age of 10 years.

Table S16. Associations between key predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity in multiple regression models stratified by child sex (N = 5686)

Predictors (IQR or reference category)	Time of assessment	zBMI		Overweight or obesity	
		β (95% CI)		OR (95% CI)	
		Girls (n = 2866)	Boys (n = 2820)	Girls (n = 2866)	Boys (n = 2820)
<i>Sociodemographic factors</i>					
Child ethnic background (ref: Dutch)	Baseline				
Non-Dutch Western		0.16 (0.05, 0.26)	0.11 (-0.01, 0.22)	1.74 (1.1, 2.76)	1.82 (1.11, 2.99)
Non-Dutch Non-Western		0.16 (0.07, 0.25)	0.06 (-0.04, 0.16)	1.92 (1.33, 2.78)	1.52 (1.04, 2.23)
Maternal education (ref: high)	Baseline				
Middle		-	-	1.93 (1.34, 2.78)	1.1 (0.77, 1.58)
Low		-	-	1.86 (1.19, 2.91)	1.5 (0.94, 2.37)
Paternal education (ref: high)	Baseline				
Middle		-	-	1.53 (1.04, 2.24)	1.48 (1.02, 2.16)
Low		-	-	1.54 (0.98, 2.43)	1.43 (0.94, 2.17)
Maternal education (ref: high)	5 years				
Middle		0.12 (0.04, 0.2)	0.11 (0.03, 0.19)	-	-
Low		0.18 (0.06, 0.31)	0.21 (0.09, 0.34)	-	-
Paternal education (ref: high)	5 years				
Middle		0.08 (-0.01, 0.16)	0.1 (0.01, 0.18)	-	-
Low		0.12 (0.02, 0.23)	0.06 (-0.06, 0.18)	-	-
<i>Preconception and prenatal parental health</i>					
Maternal BMI (4.4 kg/m ²)	Before pregnancy	0.19 (0.16, 0.23)	0.15 (0.1, 0.19)	1.55 (1.34, 1.8)	1.39 (1.2, 1.61)
Paternal BMI (4.2 kg/m ²)	Baseline	0.16 (0.12, 0.2)	0.18 (0.13, 0.23)	1.5 (1.25, 1.8)	1.47 (1.22, 1.77)
Maternal smoking (ref: no)	Baseline				
Until pregnancy		0.04 (-0.07, 0.15)	0.01 (-0.11, 0.12)	1.5 (0.96, 2.33)	0.74 (0.43, 1.27)
Continued		0.19 (0.09, 0.28)	0.04 (-0.05, 0.13)	1.47 (1.01, 2.13)	1.15 (0.80, 1.64)
<i>Maternal nutrition during pregnancy</i>					
Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids (3.3%)	During pregnancy	-	-	1.15 (0.94, 1.42)	1.21 (0.97, 1.5)
Vitamin D status, 25(OH)D (48.4 nmol/L)	During pregnancy	-0.05 (-0.11, 0)	-0.11 (-0.18, -0.04)	0.7 (0.53, 0.93)	0.84 (0.63, 1.11)
Folic acid supplement use (ref: start periconceptional)	During pregnancy				
Start first 10 weeks		0.07 (0, 0.14)	0.08 (-0.01, 0.16)	1.13 (0.8, 1.59)	1.46 (1, 2.13)

Never		0.06 (-0.05, 0.18)	0.04 (-0.08, 0.16)	1.2 (0.76, 1.9)	1.34 (0.84, 2.15)
Milk intake (ref: <1 glasses)	During pregnancy				
1 – <2 glasses		0.02 (-0.06, 0.1)	0 (-0.08, 0.08)	1.07 (0.74, 1.57)	0.78 (0.55, 1.11)
2 – <3 glasses		0 (-0.09, 0.08)	0.03 (-0.07, 0.12)	0.89 (0.6, 1.34)	0.79 (0.51, 1.22)
≥3 glasses		0.06 (-0.05, 0.16)	0.05 (-0.06, 0.15)	1.23 (0.76, 1.99)	1.03 (0.67, 1.56)
<i>Maternal mental health and parenting</i>					
The timing of the introduction of solid foods (ref: ≥5 months)	During infancy				
4-<5 months		-	-	1.18 (0.77, 1.8)	1.2 (0.75, 1.93)
<4 months		-	-	1.3 (0.78, 2.18)	1.18 (0.67, 2.07)
Breastfeeding duration (ref: ≥6 months)	During infancy				
4-<6 months		-	-	1.39 (0.85, 2.27)	0.87 (0.52, 1.47)
2-<4 months		-	-	1.24 (0.79, 1.92)	0.78 (0.5, 1.22)
<2 months		-	-	0.97 (0.64, 1.45)	0.86 (0.54, 1.36)
Pressure to eat (6 unit of sum score)	4 years	-0.04 (-0.09, 0)	-0.05 (-0.1, 0)	-	-
Restriction (9 units of sum score)	10 years	0.18 (0.13, 0.24)	0.17 (0.11, 0.23)	1.53 (1.21, 1.93)	1.61 (1.24, 2.09)
<i>Early-life weight and weight gain</i>					
Weight gain during infancy (1110 g)	0 to 6 months	0.08 (0.03, 0.14)	0.06 (0, 0.11)	-	-
Weight gain during infancy (760 g)	6 to 12 months	0.08 (0.03, 0.12)	0.06 (0.02, 0.1)	1.27 (1.04, 1.54)	1.14 (0.96, 1.35)
Weight gain during infancy (1100 g)	12 to 24 months	0.11 (0.06, 0.15)	0.1 (0.05, 0.15)	1.36 (1.13, 1.62)	1.21 (0.99, 1.48)
zBMI (1.3 SD)	1.5 months	0.08 (0.03, 0.14)	0.07 (0.01, 0.13)	1.4 (1.11, 1.75)	1.23 (0.98, 1.54)
zBMI (1.4 SD)	2 years	0.27 (0.19, 0.34)	0.29 (0.23, 0.36)	1.92 (1.5, 2.46)	1.83 (1.46, 2.29)
BMI at estimated adiposity peak (1.1 kg/m ²)	-	0.16 (0.09, 0.24)	0.19 (0.12, 0.26)	-	-
<i>Infant and childhood nutrition</i>					
High fat-mass dietary pattern (1.2 unit of component scores)	1 year	0.05 (0.01, 0.1)	0.05 (-0.01, 0.11)	1.15 (0.91, 1.45)	1.13 (0.94, 1.37)
Animal and plant protein intake (15.8 g)	1 year	0.03 (-0.02, 0.08)	0.02 (-0.03, 0.07)	1.09 (0.91, 1.31)	1.09 (0.9, 1.33)
<i>Child behaviors</i>					
Enjoyment of food (4 units of sum score)	4 years	-0.03 (-0.09, 0.02)	-0.06 (-0.12, 0.00)	-	-
Emotional overeating (4 units of sum score)	10 years	-	-	1.11 (0.91, 1.35)	1.15 (0.93, 1.42)
Food responsiveness (5 units of sum score)	10 years	0.22 (0.18, 0.26)	0.27 (0.22, 0.32)	2.09 (1.77, 2.48)	2.24 (1.88, 2.68)
Satiety responsiveness (8 units of sum score)	10 years	-0.19 (-0.24, -0.15)	-0.17 (-0.22, -0.12)	0.57 (0.46, 0.71)	0.71 (0.58, 0.87)
Breakfast skipping (ref: no)	6 years	0.19 (0.05, 0.32)	0.25 (0.11, 0.39)	1.86 (1.13, 3.07)	1.69 (1.04, 2.72)
Television viewing (ref: <2 hours/day)	6 years	0.05 (-0.02, 0.12)	0.1 (0.02, 0.18)	-	-
Outdoor play (ref: >1 hour/day)	6 years	-	-	0.81 (0.53, 1.25)	1.02 (0.68, 1.53)

Set-shifting (10 units of sum score)	4 years	-0.1 (-0.14, -0.05)	-0.03 (-0.08, 0.01)	0.72 (0.57, 0.91)	1.02 (0.83, 1.26)
Explained variance (R^2)		52.5% (49.6%, 55.3%)	46.0% (42.8%, 48.9%)	38.4% ^a	30.7 % ^a

Predictors selected in at least 10% DSA models were identified as key predictors. Since the DSA algorithm was performed separately for zBMI and weight status, a set of key predictors was identified for each outcome. These key predictors were then included simultaneously in the multiple linear regression model for zBMI and the logistic regression model for weight status, respectively. Predictors not modeled in a given outcome were marked with a ‘-’ in the table.

For continuous variables, β represent differences in zBMI per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, β represents differences of zBMI in comparison category vs. reference categories. For continuous variables, OR represent differences in odds of overweight and obesity per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, OR represent differences of odds of overweight and obesity in comparison category vs. reference categories. IQR and reference categories are indicated in the bracket for predictors. Models include all key predictors selected by the DSA algorithm.

^a McFadden’s pseudo R^2 was calculated for explained variance in the odds of being overweight and obesity at the age of 10 years.

Table S17. Associations between key predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity in multiple regression models stratified by child ethnic background (N = 5686)

Predictors (IQR or reference category)	Time of assessment	zBMI		Overweight or obesity	
		β (95% CI)		OR (95% CI)	
		Dutch (n = 3417)	Non-Dutch (n = 2269)	Dutch (n = 3417)	Non-Dutch (n = 2269)
<i>Sociodemographic factors</i>					
Maternal education (ref: high)	Baseline	-	-		
Middle		-	-	1.41 (0.99, 2.01)	1.40 (0.98, 2.01)
Low				2.01 (1.22, 3.29)	1.33 (0.87, 2.03)
Paternal education (ref: high)	Baseline	-	-		
Middle		-	-	2.03 (1.4, 2.92)	1.10 (0.75, 1.62)
Low				1.99 (1.22, 3.25)	1.18 (0.79, 1.77)
Maternal education (ref: high)	5 years				
Middle		0.11 (0.04, 0.18)	0.10 (0.00, 0.20)	-	-
Low		0.32 (0.18, 0.45)	0.10 (-0.03, 0.24)	-	-
Paternal education (ref: high)	5 years				
Middle		0.12 (0.05, 0.19)	0.03 (-0.08, 0.14)	-	-
Low		0.08 (-0.03, 0.18)	0.09 (-0.05, 0.23)	-	-
<i>Preconception and prenatal parental health</i>					
Maternal BMI (4.4 kg/m ²)	Before pregnancy	0.18 (0.15, 0.21)	0.15 (0.11, 0.20)	1.57 (1.36, 1.81)	1.38 (1.19, 1.59)
Paternal BMI (4.2 kg/m ²)	Baseline	0.19 (0.15, 0.23)	0.15 (0.09, 0.21)	1.54 (1.29, 1.84)	1.43 (1.17, 1.74)
Maternal smoking (ref: no)	Baseline				
Until pregnancy		0.03 (-0.06, 0.13)	0.02 (-0.13, 0.17)	1.25 (0.79, 1.98)	1.05 (0.62, 1.78)
Continued		0.16 (0.08, 0.24)	0.04 (-0.07, 0.15)	1.53 (1.04, 2.26)	1.10 (0.78, 1.55)
<i>Maternal nutrition during pregnancy</i>					
Total n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids percentage by weight of total sum of fatty acids (3.3%)	During pregnancy	-	-	1.18 (0.92, 1.50)	1.21 (0.99, 1.49)
Vitamin D status, 25(OH)D (48.4 nmol/L)	During pregnancy	-0.07 (-0.12, -0.02)	-0.11 (-0.19, -0.03)	0.75 (0.57, 0.97)	0.72 (0.55, 0.95)
Folic acid supplement use (ref: start periconceptional)	During pregnancy				
Start first 10 weeks		0.06 (0.00, 0.12)	0.11 (-0.01, 0.23)	1.33 (0.96, 1.83)	1.19 (0.78, 1.81)
Never		0.00 (-0.10, 0.11)	0.11 (-0.03, 0.24)	1.13 (0.68, 1.88)	1.36 (0.90, 2.07)
Milk intake (ref: <1 glasses)	During pregnancy				

1 – <2 glasses		0.03 (-0.05, 0.10)	-0.03 (-0.12, 0.07)	0.98 (0.65, 1.49)	0.83 (0.58, 1.18)
2 – <3 glasses		0.02 (-0.05, 0.09)	-0.01 (-0.14, 0.11)	0.91 (0.61, 1.37)	0.71 (0.46, 1.11)
≥3 glasses		0.05 (-0.03, 0.13)	0.04 (-0.10, 0.19)	1.27 (0.83, 1.92)	0.98 (0.60, 1.61)
<i>Maternal mental health and parenting</i>					
The timing of the introduction of solid foods (ref: ≥5 months)	During infancy				
4-<5 months		-	-	1.12 (0.73, 1.74)	1.21 (0.75, 1.95)
<4 months		-	-	1.08 (0.61, 1.9)	1.29 (0.78, 2.15)
Breastfeeding duration (ref: ≥6 months)	During infancy				
4-<6 months		-	-	1.33 (0.82, 2.14)	0.90 (0.52, 1.57)
2-<4 months		-	-	0.93 (0.59, 1.46)	1.03 (0.67, 1.57)
<2 months		-	-	0.84 (0.54, 1.32)	0.96 (0.63, 1.45)
Pressure to eat (6 unit of sum score)	4 years	-0.04 (-0.07, 0.00)	-0.07 (-0.13, 0.00)	-	-
Restriction (9 units of sum score)	10 years	0.16 (0.11, 0.21)	0.19 (0.12, 0.27)	1.75 (1.32, 2.32)	1.43 (1.11, 1.84)
<i>Early-life weight and weight gain</i>					
Weight gain during infancy (1110 g)	0 to 6 months	0.05 (0.00, 0.09)	0.08 (0.01, 0.14)	-	-
Weight gain during infancy (760 g)	6 to 12 months	0.05 (0.01, 0.09)	0.08 (0.03, 0.14)	1.1 (0.92, 1.31)	1.26 (1.03, 1.55)
Weight gain during infancy (1100 g)	12 to 24 months	0.08 (0.04, 0.12)	0.13 (0.07, 0.19)	1.21 (1.01, 1.46)	1.35 (1.1, 1.64)
zBMI (1.3 SD)	1.5 months	0.06 (0.01, 0.11)	0.1 (0.03, 0.17)	1.35 (1.09, 1.67)	1.26 (1.01, 1.56)
zBMI (1.4 SD)	2 years	0.24 (0.19, 0.29)	0.33 (0.25, 0.42)	1.79 (1.41, 2.26)	1.93 (1.54, 2.42)
BMI at estimated adiposity peak (1.1 kg/m ²)	-	0.21 (0.15, 0.27)	0.13 (0.05, 0.21)	-	-
<i>Infant and childhood nutrition</i>					
High fat-mass dietary pattern (1.2 unit of component scores)	1 year	0.06 (0.01, 0.11)	0.05 (-0.02, 0.13)	1.19 (0.92, 1.54)	1.12 (0.91, 1.37)
Animal and plant protein intake (15.8 g)	1 year	0.03 (-0.01, 0.07)	0.02 (-0.04, 0.07)	1.12 (0.89, 1.42)	1.05 (0.9, 1.23)
<i>Child behaviors</i>					
Enjoyment of food (4 units of sum score)	4 years	-0.06 (-0.1, -0.01)	-0.04 (-0.1, 0.02)	-	-
Emotional overeating (4 units of sum score)	10 years	-	-	1.13 (0.92, 1.38)	1.14 (0.93, 1.4)
Food responsiveness (5 units of sum score)	10 years	0.24 (0.20, 0.27)	0.26 (0.20, 0.32)	2.27 (1.86, 2.76)	2.09 (1.72, 2.53)
Satiety responsiveness (8 units of sum score)	10 years	-0.18 (-0.22, -0.14)	-0.19 (-0.25, -0.13)	0.64 (0.52, 0.80)	0.64 (0.52, 0.78)
Breakfast skipping (ref: no)	6 years	0.12 (-0.03, 0.28)	0.27 (0.12, 0.41)	1.24 (0.59, 2.62)	2.02 (1.32, 3.09)
Television viewing (ref: <2 hours/day)	6 years	0.07 (0.01, 0.12)	0.08 (-0.02, 0.19)	-	-
Outdoor play (ref: >1 hour/day)	6 years	-	-	1.14 (0.71, 1.81)	0.81 (0.56, 1.16)
Set-shifting (10 units of sum score)	4 years	-0.05 (-0.09, -0.02)	-0.07 (-0.13, -0.01)	0.86 (0.7, 1.06)	0.81 (0.65, 1.02)

Explained variance (R^2)		46.1% (43.2%, 48.9%)	48.9% (45.5%, 52.2%)	33.5% ^a	30.2% ^a
--	--	-------------------------	-------------------------	--------------------	--------------------

Predictors selected in at least 10% DSA models were identified as key predictors. Since the DSA algorithm was performed separately for zBMI and weight status, a set of key predictors was identified for each outcome. These key predictors were then included simultaneously in the multiple linear regression model for zBMI and the logistic regression model for weight status, respectively. Predictors not modeled in a given outcome were marked with a ‘-’ in the table.

For continuous variables, β represents differences in zBMI per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, β represents differences of zBMI in comparison category vs. reference categories. For continuous variables, OR represent differences in odds of overweight and obesity per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, OR represent differences of odds of overweight and obesity in comparison category vs. reference categories. IQR and reference categories are indicated in the bracket for predictors. Models include all key predictors selected by the DSA algorithm.

^a McFadden’s pseudo R^2 was calculated for explained variance in the odds of being overweight and obesity at the age of 10 years.

Table S18. Associations between predictors and zBMI or overweight and obesity at age 10 years in parsimonious multiple regression models (N = 5686)

Predictors (IQR or reference category)	Time of assessment	zBMI β (95% CI)	Overweight or obesity OR (95% CI)
<i>Sociodemographic factors</i>			
Child ethnic background (ref: Dutch)	Baseline		
Non-Dutch Western		-	2.16 (1.60, 2.92)
Non-Dutch Non-Western		-	2.37 (1.94, 2.88)
Maternal education (ref: high)	Baseline		
Middle		-	1.68 (1.33, 2.12)
Low		-	2.34 (1.78, 3.07)
Paternal education (ref: high)	Baseline		
Middle		0.18 (0.13, 0.24)	1.54 (1.18, 2.00)
Low		0.26 (0.20, 0.32)	1.58 (1.18, 2.13)
<i>Preconception and prenatal parental health</i>			
Maternal BMI (4.4 kg/m ²)	Before pregnancy	0.19 (0.15, 0.23)	1.49 (1.35, 1.65)
Paternal BMI (4.2 kg/m ²)	Baseline	0.19 (0.16, 0.22)	1.50 (1.31, 1.72)
<i>Maternal nutrition during pregnancy</i>			
Vitamin D status, 25(OH)D (48.4 nmol/L)	During pregnancy	-0.14 (-0.18, -0.10)	-
<i>Maternal mental health and parenting</i>			
Restriction (9 units of sum score)	10 years	0.18 (0.14, 0.23)	1.59 (1.34, 1.88)
<i>Early-life weight and weight gain</i>			
Weight gain during infancy (1100 g)	12 to 24 months	-	1.28 (1.12, 1.45)
zBMI (1.4 SD)	2 years	0.34 (0.29, 0.39)	2.01 (1.71, 2.35)
BMI at estimated adiposity peak (1.1 kg/m ²)	-	0.24 (0.20, 0.29)	-
<i>Infant and childhood nutrition</i>			
High fat-mass dietary pattern (1.2 unit of component scores)	1 year	0.07 (0.04, 0.11)	-
<i>Child behaviors</i>			
Food responsiveness (5 units of sum score)	10 years	0.25 (0.22, 0.29)	2.18 (1.94, 2.44)
Satiety responsiveness (8 units of sum score)	10 years	-0.19 (-0.22, -0.16)	0.64 (0.55, 0.73)
Explained variance (R²)		46.4% (44.0%, 48.6%)	31.3% ^a

DSA algorithm was performed in a parsimonious way based on cross-validation risk plots, allowing up to 10 variables in each model. Predictors selected in at least 10% DSA models were identified as key predictors. Since the DSA algorithm was performed separately for zBMI and weight status, a set of key predictors was identified for each outcome. These key predictors were then included simultaneously in the multiple linear regression model for zBMI and the logistic regression model for weight status, respectively. Predictors not modeled in a given outcome were marked with a ‘-’ in the table.

For continuous variables, β represent differences in zBMI per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, β represent differences of zBMI in comparison category vs. reference categories. For continuous variables, OR represent differences in odds of overweight and obesity per interquartile range increase in predictors; for categorical variables, OR represent differences of odds of overweight and obesity in comparison category vs. reference categories. IQR and reference categories are indicated in the bracket for predictors. Models include all key predictors selected by the DSA algorithm and child BMI polygenic risk scores.

^a McFadden’s pseudo R^2 was calculated for explained variance in the odds of being overweight and obesity at the age of 10 years.

Reference list of publications included in the evidence synthesis

- 1 Ay L, Hokken-Koelega AC, Mook-Kanamori DO, et al. Tracking and determinants of subcutaneous fat mass in early childhood: the Generation R Study. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2008; 32: 1050-9.
- 2 Benschop L, Schalekamp-Timmermans S, Roeters van Lennep JE, et al. Cardiovascular Risk Factors Track From Mother to Child. *J Am Heart Assoc*. 2018; 7: e009536.
- 3 Bouthoorn SH, van Lenthe FJ, Kiefte-de Jong JC, et al. Genetic taste blindness to bitter and body composition in childhood: a Mendelian randomization design. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2014; 38: 1005-10.
- 4 Bouthoorn SH, Wijtzes AI, Jaddoe VW, et al. Development of socioeconomic inequalities in obesity among Dutch pre-school and school-aged children. *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2014; 22: 2230-7.
- 5 Bowling AB, Tiemeier HW, Jaddoe VWV, Barker ED, Jansen PW. ADHD symptoms and body composition changes in childhood: a longitudinal study evaluating directionality of associations. *Pediatr Obes*. 2018; 13: 567-75.
- 6 Braun KV, Erler NS, Kiefte-de Jong JC, et al. Dietary Intake of Protein in Early Childhood Is Associated with Growth Trajectories between 1 and 9 Years of Age. *J Nutr*. 2016; 146: 2361-67.
- 7 Braun KV, Voortman T, Kiefte-de Jong JC, et al. Dietary Intakes of Folic Acid and Methionine in Early Childhood Are Associated with Body Composition at School Age. *J Nutr*. 2015; 145: 2123-9.
- 8 Cajachagua-Torres KN, El Marroun H, Reiss IKM, Santos S, Jaddoe VWV. Foetal tobacco and cannabis exposure, body fat and cardio-metabolic health in childhood. *Pediatr Obes*. 2022; 17: e12863.
- 9 Camfferman R, Jansen PW, Rippe RCA, et al. The association between overweight and internalizing and externalizing behavior in early childhood. *Social Science & Medicine*. 2016; 168: 35-42.
- 10 de Barse LM, Tiemeier H, Leermakers ET, et al. Longitudinal association between preschool fussy eating and body composition at 6 years of age: The Generation R Study. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2015; 12: 153.
- 11 Derks IP, Tiemeier H, Sijbrands EJ, et al. Testing the direction of effects between child body composition and restrictive feeding practices: results from a population-based cohort. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2017; 106: 783-90.
- 12 Derks IPM, Bolhuis K, Yalcin Z, et al. Testing Bidirectional Associations Between Childhood Aggression and BMI: Results from Three Cohorts. 2019.
- 13 Derks IPM, Kocavska D, Jaddoe VWV, et al. Longitudinal Associations of Sleep Duration in Infancy and Early Childhood with Body Composition and Cardiometabolic Health at the Age of 6 Years: The Generation R Study. *Child Obes*. 2017; 13: 400-08.
- 14 Derks IPM, Sijbrands EJG, Wake M, et al. Eating behavior and body composition across childhood: a prospective cohort study. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2018; 15: 96.
- 15 Durmus B, Arends LR, Ay L, et al. Parental anthropometrics, early growth and the risk of overweight in pre-school children: the Generation R Study. *Pediatr Obes*. 2013; 8: 339-50.

- 16 Durmus B, Ay L, Hokken-Koelega AC, et al. Maternal smoking during pregnancy and subcutaneous fat mass in early childhood. The Generation R Study. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 2011; 26: 295-304.
- 17 Durmus B, Heppe DH, Gishti O, et al. General and abdominal fat outcomes in school-age children associated with infant breastfeeding patterns. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2014; 99: 1351-8.
- 18 Durmus B, Heppe DH, Taal HR, et al. Parental smoking during pregnancy and total and abdominal fat distribution in school-age children: the Generation R Study. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2014; 38: 966-72.
- 19 Durmus B, Kruithof CJ, Gillman MH, et al. Parental smoking during pregnancy, early growth, and risk of obesity in preschool children: the Generation R Study. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2011; 94: 164-71.
- 20 Elhakeem A, Taylor AE, Inskip HM, et al. Association of Assisted Reproductive Technology With Offspring Growth and Adiposity From Infancy to Early Adulthood. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2022; 5: e2222106.
- 21 Ertel KA, Kleinman K, van Rossem L, et al. Maternal perinatal depression is not independently associated with child body mass index in the Generation R Study: methods and missing data matter. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2012; 65: 1300-9.
- 22 Gaillard R, Rurangirwa AA, Williams MA, et al. Maternal Parity, fetal and childhood growth, and cardiometabolic risk factors. *Hypertension*. 2014; 64: 266-74.
- 23 Gaillard R, Steegers EA, Duijts L, et al. Childhood cardiometabolic outcomes of maternal obesity during pregnancy: the Generation R Study. *Hypertension*. 2014; 63: 683-91.
- 24 Gaillard R, Steegers EA, Franco OH, Hofman A, Jaddoe VW. Maternal weight gain in different periods of pregnancy and childhood cardio-metabolic outcomes. The Generation R Study. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2015; 39: 677-85.
- 25 Gaillard R, Steegers EA, Tiemeier H, Hofman A, Jaddoe VW. Placental vascular dysfunction, fetal and childhood growth, and cardiovascular development: the generation R study. *Circulation*. 2013; 128: 2202-10.
- 26 Gishti O, Gaillard R, Felix JF, et al. Early origins of ethnic disparities in cardiovascular risk factors. *Prev Med*. 2015; 76: 84-91.
- 27 Gishti O, Gaillard R, Manniesing R, et al. Fetal and infant growth patterns associated with total and abdominal fat distribution in school-age children. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2014; 99: 2557-66.
- 28 Gishti O, Kruithof CJ, Felix JF, et al. Ethnic disparities in general and abdominal adiposity at school age: a multiethnic population-based cohort study in the Netherlands. *Ann Nutr Metab*. 2014; 64: 208-17.
- 29 Godoy GA, Korevaar TI, Peeters RP, et al. Maternal thyroid hormones during pregnancy, childhood adiposity and cardiovascular risk factors: the Generation R Study. *Clin Endocrinol (Oxf)*. 2014; 81: 117-25.
- 30 Gootjes DV, Posthumus AG, Jaddoe VWV, van Rijn BB, Steegers EAP. Maternal hypertensive disorders in pregnancy and early childhood cardiometabolic risk factors: The Generation R Study. *PLoS One*. 2021; 16: e0261351.
- 31 Guxens M, Tiemeier H, Jansen PW, et al. Parental psychological distress during pregnancy and early growth in preschool children: the generation R study. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2013; 177: 538-47.
- 32 Harris HA, Bowling A, Santos S, Greaves-Lord K, Jansen PW. Child ADHD and autistic traits, eating behaviours and weight: A population-based study. *Pediatr Obes*. 2022; 17.

- 33 Jaddoe VW, de Jonge LL, Hofman A, et al. First trimester fetal growth restriction and cardiovascular risk factors in school age children: population based cohort study. *Bmj*. 2014; 348: g14.
- 34 Jansen MA, Kiefte-de Jong JC, Gaillard R, et al. Growth trajectories and bone mineral density in anti-tissue transglutaminase antibody-positive children: the Generation R Study. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2015; 13: 913-20 e5.
- 35 Jansen PW, Derks IPM, Batenburg A, et al. Using Food to Soothe in Infancy is Prospectively Associated with Childhood BMI in a Population-Based Cohort. *J Nutr*. 2019; 149: 788-94.
- 36 Jansen PW, Derks IPM, Mou YC, et al. Associations of parents' use of food as reward with children's eating behaviour and BMI in a population-based cohort. *Pediatr Obes*. 2020; 15.
- 37 Jansen PW, Roza SJ, Jaddoe VW, et al. Children's eating behavior, feeding practices of parents and weight problems in early childhood: results from the population-based Generation R Study. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2012; 9: 130.
- 38 Jansen PW, Tharner A, van der Ende J, et al. Feeding practices and child weight: is the association bidirectional in preschool children? *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2014; 100: 1329-36.
- 39 Jelena Vidakovic A, Santos S, Williams MA, et al. Maternal plasma n-3 and n-6 polyunsaturated fatty acid concentrations during pregnancy and subcutaneous fat mass in infancy. *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2016; 24: 1759-66.
- 40 Jen V, Braun KVE, Karagounis LG, et al. Longitudinal association of dietary protein intake in infancy and adiposity throughout childhood. *Clin Nutr*. 2019; 38: 1296-302.
- 41 Jen V, Erler NS, Tielemans MJ, et al. Mothers' intake of sugar-containing beverages during pregnancy and body composition of their children during childhood: the Generation R Study. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2017; 105: 834-41.
- 42 Jharap VV, Santos S, Steegers EAP, Jaddoe VWV, Gaillard R. Associations of maternal obesity and excessive weight gain during pregnancy with subcutaneous fat mass in infancy. *Early Hum Dev*. 2017; 108: 23-28.
- 43 Kooijman MN, Gaillard R, Reiss I, et al. Influence of fetal blood flow redistribution on fetal and childhood growth and fat distribution: the Generation R Study. *Bjog*. 2016; 123: 2104-12.
- 44 Kruithof CJ, Gishti O, Hofman A, Gaillard R, Jaddoe VW. Infant weight growth velocity patterns and general and abdominal adiposity in school-age children. The Generation R Study. *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2016; 70: 1144-50.
- 45 Lecorguillé M, Schipper MC, O'Donnell A, et al. Impact of parental lifestyle patterns in the preconception and pregnancy periods on childhood obesity. *Frontiers in Nutrition*. 2023; 10.
- 46 Leermakers ET, Felix JF, Erler NS, et al. Sugar-containing beverage intake in toddlers and body composition up to age 6 years: the Generation R study. *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2015; 69: 314-21.
- 47 Leermakers ET, Felix JF, Jaddoe VW, et al. Sugar-containing beverage intake at the age of 1 year and cardiometabolic health at the age of 6 years: the Generation R Study. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2015; 12: 114.
- 48 Leermakers ET, Kiefte-de Jong JC, Hofman A, Jaddoe VW, Franco OH. Lutein intake at the age of 1 year and cardiometabolic health at the age of 6 years: the Generation R Study. *Br J Nutr*. 2015; 114: 970-8.

- 49 Lin LZ, Yang-Huang JW, Wang HJ, et al. Social mobility by parent education and childhood overweight and obesity: a prospective cohort study. *Eur J Public Health*. 2021; 31: 764-70.
- 50 Maas JA, Mook-Kanamori DO, Ay L, et al. Insulin VNTR and IGF-1 promoter region polymorphisms are not associated with body composition in early childhood: the generation R study. *Horm Res Paediatr*. 2010; 73: 120-7.
- 51 Mackenbach JD, Tiemeier H, Ende J, et al. Relation of emotional and behavioral problems with body mass index in preschool children: the Generation R study. *J Dev Behav Pediatr*. 2012; 33: 641-8.
- 52 Marinkovic T, Toemen L, Kruithof CJ, et al. Early Infant Growth Velocity Patterns and Cardiovascular and Metabolic Outcomes in Childhood. *J Pediatr*. 2017; 186: 57-63 e4.
- 53 Miliku K, Felix JF, Voortman T, et al. Associations of maternal and fetal vitamin D status with childhood body composition and cardiovascular risk factors. *Matern Child Nutr*. 2018; 15: e12672.
- 54 Monasso GS, Santos S, Geurtsen ML, et al. Associations of Early Pregnancy and Neonatal Circulating Folate, Vitamin B-12, and Homocysteine Concentrations with Cardiometabolic Risk Factors in Children at 10 y of Age. *J Nutr*. 2021; 151: 1628-36.
- 55 Monnereau C, Jansen PW, Tiemeier H, Jaddoe VW, Felix JF. Influence of genetic variants associated with body mass index on eating behavior in childhood. *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2017; 25: 765-72.
- 56 Monnereau C, Santos S, van der Lugt A, Jaddoe VWV, Felix JF. Associations of adult genetic risk scores for adiposity with childhood abdominal, liver and pericardial fat assessed by magnetic resonance imaging. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2018; 42: 897-904.
- 57 Monnereau C, Vogelesang S, Kruithof CJ, Jaddoe VW, Felix JF. Associations of genetic risk scores based on adult adiposity pathways with childhood growth and adiposity measures. *BMC Genet*. 2016; 17: 120.
- 58 Nguyen AN, Jen V, Jaddoe VWV, et al. Diet quality in early and mid-childhood in relation to trajectories of growth and body composition. *Clin Nutr*. 2020; 39: 845-52.
- 59 Nguyen AN, Santos S, Braun KVE, Voortman T. Carbohydrate Intake in Early Childhood and Body Composition and Metabolic Health: Results from the Generation R Study. *Nutrients*. 2020; 12.
- 60 Noppe G, van den Akker EL, de Rijke YB, et al. Long-term glucocorticoid concentrations as a risk factor for childhood obesity and adverse body-fat distribution. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2016; 40: 1503-09.
- 61 Patro Golab B, Voerman E, van der Lugt A, Santos S, Jaddoe VWV. Subcutaneous fat mass in infancy and abdominal, pericardial and liver fat assessed by Magnetic Resonance Imaging at the age of 10 years. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2019; 43: 392-401.
- 62 Poeran-Bahadoer S, Jaddoe VWV, Gishti O, et al. Maternal vomiting during early pregnancy and cardiovascular risk factors at school age: the Generation R Study. *J Dev Orig Health Dis*. 2020; 11: 118-26.
- 63 Quezada-Pinedo HG, Jaddoe V, Duijts L, et al. Maternal iron status in early pregnancy and childhood body fat measures and cardiometabolic risk factors: A population-based prospective cohort. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2023; 117: 191-98.
- 64 Richmond RC, Timpson NJ, Felix JF, et al. Using Genetic Variation to Explore the Causal Effect of Maternal Pregnancy Adiposity on Future Offspring Adiposity: A Mendelian Randomisation Study. *PLoS Med*. 2017; 14: e1002221.

- 65 Santos S, Gaillard R, Oliveira A, et al. Associations of Infant Subcutaneous Fat Mass with Total and Abdominal Fat Mass at School-Age: The Generation R Study. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*. 2016; 30: 511-20.
- 66 Santos S, Monnereau C, Felix JF, et al. Maternal body mass index, gestational weight gain, and childhood abdominal, pericardial, and liver fat assessed by magnetic resonance imaging. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2019; 43: 581-93.
- 67 Steegers C, Dieleman G, Moskalenko V, et al. The longitudinal relationship between set-shifting at 4 years of age and eating disorder related features at 9 years of age in the general pediatric population. *Int J Eating Disord*. 2021.
- 68 Stroobant W, Braun KV, Kiefte-de Jong JC, et al. Intake of Different Types of Fatty Acids in Infancy Is Not Associated with Growth, Adiposity, or Cardiometabolic Health up to 6 Years of Age. *J Nutr*. 2017; 147: 413-20.
- 69 Taal HR, Vd Heijden AJ, Steegers EA, Hofman A, Jaddoe VW. Small and large size for gestational age at birth, infant growth, and childhood overweight. *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2013; 21: 1261-8.
- 70 Tielemans MJ, Steegers EAP, Voortman T, et al. Protein intake during pregnancy and offspring body composition at 6 years: the Generation R Study. *Eur J Nutr*. 2017; 56: 2151-60.
- 71 van den Broek M, Leermakers ET, Jaddoe VW, et al. Maternal dietary patterns during pregnancy and body composition of the child at age 6 y: the Generation R Study. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2015; 102: 873-80.
- 72 van Rossem L, Silva LM, Hokken-Koelega A, et al. Socioeconomic status is not inversely associated with overweight in preschool children. *J Pediatr*. 2010; 157: 929-35 e1.
- 73 Vehmeijer FOL, C CVS, Derks IPM, et al. Associations of Maternal Psychological Distress during Pregnancy with Childhood General and Organ Fat Measures. *Child Obes*. 2019; 15: 313-22.
- 74 Vehmeijer FOL, Santos S, Gaillard R, et al. Associations of Hair Cortisol Concentrations with General and Organ Fat Measures in Childhood. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2021; 106: e551-e61.
- 75 Velders FP, De Wit JE, Jansen PW, et al. FTO at rs9939609, food responsiveness, emotional control and symptoms of ADHD in preschool children. *PLoS One*. 2012; 7: e49131.
- 76 Vidakovic AJ, Gishti O, Voortman T, et al. Maternal plasma PUFA concentrations during pregnancy and childhood adiposity: the Generation R Study. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2016; 103: 1017-25.
- 77 Vinther JL, Cadman T, Avraam D, et al. Gestational age at birth and body size from infancy through adolescence: An individual participant data meta-analysis on 253,810 singletons in 16 birth cohort studies. *PLoS Med*. 2023; 20: e1004036.
- 78 Voerman E, Gaillard R, Geurtsen ML, Jaddoe VWV. Maternal First-Trimester Cow-Milk Intake Is Positively Associated with Childhood General and Abdominal Visceral Fat Mass and Lean Mass but Not with Other Cardiometabolic Risk Factors at the Age of 10 Years. *Journal of Nutrition*. 2021; 151: 1965-75.
- 79 Voerman E, Jaddoe VW, Gishti O, et al. Maternal caffeine intake during pregnancy, early growth, and body fat distribution at school age. *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2016; 24: 1170-7.
- 80 Voerman E, Jaddoe VW, Hulst ME, Oei EH, Gaillard R. Associations of maternal caffeine intake during pregnancy with abdominal and liver fat deposition in childhood. *Pediatr Obes*. 2020; 15: e12607.

- 81 Vogelezang S, Gishti O, Felix JF, et al. Tracking of abdominal subcutaneous and preperitoneal fat mass during childhood. The Generation R Study. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2016; 40: 595-600.
- 82 Vogelezang S, Monnereau C, Gaillard R, et al. Adult adiposity susceptibility loci, early growth and general and abdominal fatness in childhood: the Generation R Study. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2015; 39: 1001-9.
- 83 Vogelezang S, Santos S, Toemen L, et al. Associations of Fetal and Infant Weight Change With General, Visceral, and Organ Adiposity at School Age. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2019; 2: e192843.
- 84 Vogelezang S, Santos S, van der Beek EM, et al. Infant breastfeeding and childhood general, visceral, liver, and pericardial fat measures assessed by magnetic resonance imaging. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2018; 108: 722-29.
- 85 Voortman T, Braun KV, Kiefte-de Jong JC, et al. Protein intake in early childhood and body composition at the age of 6 years: The Generation R Study. *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2016; 40: 1018-25.
- 86 Voortman T, Leermakers ET, Franco OH, et al. A priori and a posteriori dietary patterns at the age of 1 year and body composition at the age of 6 years: the Generation R Study. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 2016; 31: 775-83.
- 87 Voortman T, Tielemans MJ, Stroobant W, et al. Plasma fatty acid patterns during pregnancy and child's growth, body composition, and cardiometabolic health: The Generation R Study. *Clin Nutr*. 2018; 37: 984-92.
- 88 Wahab RJ, Jaddoe VWV, Gaillard R. Associations of maternal early-pregnancy dietary glycemic index with childhood general, abdominal and ectopic fat accumulation. *Clin Nutr*. 2021; 40: 1628-36.
- 89 Wahab RJ, Voerman E, Jansen PW, et al. Maternal Glucose Concentrations in Early Pregnancy and Cardiometabolic Risk Factors in Childhood. *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2020; 28: 985-93.
- 90 Welten M, Gaillard R, Hofman A, de Jonge LL, Jaddoe VW. Maternal haemoglobin levels and cardio-metabolic risk factors in childhood: the Generation R study. *Bjog*. 2015; 122: 805-15.
- 91 Wijtzes AI, Bouthoorn SH, Jansen W, et al. Sedentary behaviors, physical activity behaviors, and body fat in 6-year-old children: the generation R study. *Int J Behav Nutr Phys Act*. 2014; 11: 96.
- 92 Wijtzes AI, Jansen W, Bouthoorn SH, et al. Meal-Skipping Behaviors and Body Fat in 6-Year-Old Children. *J Pediatr*. 2016; 168: 118-25 e2.
- 93 Wijtzes AI, Kooijman MN, Kiefte-de Jong JC, et al. Correlates of physical activity in 2-year-old toddlers: the generation R study. *J Pediatr*. 2013; 163: 791-9 e1-2.

A) Pooled effect sizes for BMI at 2 and 3 years

B) Pooled effect sizes for BMI at 4 years

C) Pooled effect sizes for BMI at 6 years

D) Pooled effect sizes for BMI at 10 years

Figure S1. Forest plots for predictors of child BMI with pooled effect sizes above the threshold ($|d| \geq 0.1$)

A) BMI

B) Overweight and obesity

Figure S2. Cross-validation plots based on DSA-selected models for (A) BMI and (B) overweight and obesity in children aged 10 years